

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D3.4

Software and accompanying report on developed improved procedure for OEF

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Responsible Partner:	University of Alicante
Version:	3.0
Date:	16/12/2020
Distribution level:	Public

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Comments
13/11/2020	1.0	Sergio Molina	First Draft
11/12/2020	2.0	Sergio Molina	Second Draft
16/12/2020	3.0	Sergio Molina	Final Draft

LIST OF PARTNERS

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KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
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EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
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YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
AUTH	National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience
BMC	Bayesian Magnitude Completeness
CSM	Capacity Spectrum Method
CV	Coefficient of Variation
ESHM13	The 2013 Euro-Mediterranean Seismic Hazard Model
ETAS	Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequence
FSBG	Fault Source and BackGround model
GMPE	Ground Motion Prediction Equation
GR	Gutenberg-Richter
IDCM	Improved Displacement Coefficient Method
IM	Intensity measure
IMO	Iceland Meteorological Office
ISC	International Seismological Centre
MADRS	Modified Capacity Spectrum Method
MCMC	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
MDR	Mean damage ratio
NGA	Next Generation Attenuation
OEF	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
PSHA	Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment
RPOR	Rekjanes Peninsula Oblique Rift
SEIFA	SEismicity and Faults model
SHARE	Seismic Hazard hARmonization in Europe
SISZ	South Iceland Seismic Zone
SSNTD	Solid State Nuclear Track Detector
TB	Testbed
TIR	Thermal Infrared
TLD	Thermoluminescent Detector
TFZ	Tjörnes Fracture Zone

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Task 3.2 has developed a flexible and extendable procedure for Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF) taking account of short-term changes in the seismic hazard and the uncertainties associated with these changes. The following sections summarize the main steps followed to develop the proposed methodology and corresponding software.

1.1 ETAS forecasting model

The ETAS (Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequences) seismicity model is used widely for short-term OEF, in particular after a large earthquake. This model has been implemented within the TURNkey platform for the development of an operational system for computing short-term seismicity forecasts and has been successfully applied to Testbed 3 (south Iceland) and Testbed 4 (Patras/Aegio region of Greece). The ETAS model provides spatial earthquake occurrence rates for magnitudes larger than a defined threshold for a specific forecasting time interval. The short-term forecasting time interval can range from hours to weeks.

In order to apply the Bayesian ETAS model, the following inputs are required: 1) an earthquake catalogue comprising all the events in a specific seismic sequence and 2) an aftershock zone covering the geographical distribution of the seismic sequence.

The model is applied to generate retrospective daily seismicity forecasts maps following the 17 June 2000 earthquake in south Iceland. This target seismic sequence started on the 17 June 2000 at 15:40:41 UTC when a Mw 6.4 event (the first large earthquake in June 2000) occurred. Seismicity forecast maps for earthquakes with magnitudes above different thresholds (e.g. 4.5, 5.5 and 6.5) and their corresponding uncertainties are computed. The quite noticeable uncertainties highlight the importance of incorporating a Bayesian-based parameter estimation for forecasting purposes.

The study of the June 2000 earthquake sequence proved that the Bayesian sequence-based ETAS model is not capable of forecasting a strong earthquake or even any elevated seismicity rate using only a limited number of foreshocks. However, provided a sufficient number of aftershocks in the aftermath of a large earthquake, the sequence-based ETAS model can forecast the increase in the seismicity rate along with its corresponding spatial zone.

1.2 Reasenberg and Jones forecasting model

Reasenberg and Jones (1989) is a well-known and commonly-used statistical model to forecast the aftershock rate following a mainshock. The proposed model combines the modified Omori decay of aftershocks (Utsu 1957), the Gutenberg-Richter magnitude-frequency distribution (Gutenberg and Richter 1944), and the Utsu aftershock productivity (Utsu 1972). This model has been applied to Testbed 4 (Patras/Aegio region) using an earthquake catalogue gathered from the International Seismological Centre (ISC). The methodology is described in Section 3.2, and the results for Testbed 4 are provided in Section 4.2.

1.3 Seismic activity rates forecast from radon measurements

A thorough literature review of the current state of the art trying to correlate non-seismic information with seismicity was carried out. It is observed that radon emissions from the earth before earthquakes present great interest to the scientific community working in earthquake precursors, so a model to estimate the daily seismic activity rate with a threshold magnitude using radon measurements is proposed.

From the alpha decay of radium, radon atoms have enough kinetic energy to move from the site where radon is generated to where it can be recorded. The radon observed in the case of anomalies correlated with geophysical events may be considered as having two possible origins. Either it is produced at depth or, once produced locally, it is displaced by other interstitial fluids whose motion is triggered by geodynamical events. Currently, the local origin hypothesis seems to be the most reliable, which is also supported by experiments.

The literature review concludes that most of the studies try to correlate the occurrence of an impending earthquake with changes in radon data, e.g.: anomalies exceeding two standard deviations, positive and negative variations from a given average or “splashes” from the average radon concentration followed by a sharp decrease. However, the choice of the average values (annual, seasonal, monthly) varies depending on the researcher, making it complicated to define what an anomaly is. Finally, the anomaly is usually related to a precursor time which ranges between 2 days and 3 weeks in almost all of the studied papers after 2005. Currently there is no reliable relationship between radon emission that allows the prediction of an imminent earthquake. This kind of relationships cannot be obtained by only gathering values from literature but should be developed using reliable data from a network of stations situated at different distances from the seismogenic source.

There is consensus in the literature review regarding detection of anomalies due to seismicity with an epicentral distance that is correlated to the size of the earthquakes. So, radon anomalies from small earthquakes can only be detected if they are located close to the station and radon anomalies from larger earthquakes can be detected even far from the station. Besides, the radon anomalies can start before the occurrence of the earthquake and can last days, weeks, or months after the event. Hence, the radon measurement may represent a cumulative function of the seismic activity rate in the region. Subsequently, we have correlated the daily seismic change in the seismic activity rate over a threshold magnitude with the radon gas emissions (or corresponding anomalies).

One radon station located in the Vrancea region (Romania) has been used to record the daily values of radon concentration in that region. Seasonal and linear trends have been removed from the radon signal to remove the influence of non-seismic factors. Additionally, the daily seismic activity rates for different threshold magnitudes are obtained from an earthquake catalogue covering the radon measurement time period and the influence area of the radon station. Then, a correlation model between both variables (smoothed using a 30-day moving average filter) is obtained. The results from the model can be expressed as the increment in the percentage of the daily seismic activity rate over the background seismicity for a threshold magnitude, which can be later used to compute short-term probabilistic seismic hazard analysis but they cannot be used to forecast any impending earthquake in the region.

1.4 Short-term probabilistic seismic hazard analysis

ETAS results have been used to assess the short-term time-dependent seismic hazard for Testbeds 3 and 4. Additionally, the results for Testbed 4 have also incorporated the results from the radon model through a logic tree accounting for the uncertainties in these correlations.

Regarding Testbed 3 in south Iceland, the short-term spatial seismicity rates are calculated using the Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model. A logic tree is defined based on three branching levels: depths of events, possible maximum magnitude, and ground motion prediction equations. In total, 36 logic

tree branches are generated to capture the epistemic uncertainty in the hazard analyses. For the 18 June 2000 forecasting interval, the daily probability of exceedance of 0.5 g from conventional hazard assessment in Hveragerði is 4×10^{-5} , while for the short-term PSHA, the daily probability of exceeding 0.5 g is forecasted as 6×10^{-3} , meaning that the daily forecast hazard increased 150 times with respect to the conventional hazard value.

Regarding Testbed 4 in Greece, the ETAS results are used to compute the short-term time-dependent probabilistic seismic hazard analysis in the aftershock zone using the same input parameters as in the 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model (ESHM13). The short-term hazard curve increases, during the considered seismic sequences, when compared with the conventional hazard curve, which constitutes the lower bound hazard. Finally, a logic tree is used to compute the short-term hazard curve by combining the increase of seismic activity rate due to the radon measurement and the ETAS model. The increase in the seismicity due to radon is obtained based on a correlation model between the radon measurements and the seismicity rate. The obtained results confirmed that the employment of the non-seismic information does not have a strong influence on the final hazard, at least with the values assumed in this study. This non-seismic branch should not have a high weighting in the logic-tree since the model is only based on a specific region (Vrancea, Romania), the radon data covers a limited time period (from 2016 to 2020), and the seismic events never exceeded magnitude 5.5 during that period.

1.5 Time-dependent loss

The goal of any OEF is to provide effective parameters that can be employed to recommend mitigation actions. These mitigation actions can be better attributed to short-term time-dependent loss than hazard estimates, because the obtained losses can be used to conduct a simple cost-benefit analysis (or a more sophisticated type of decision making) to assess in which cases the proposed actions are favourable.

Therefore, the open-source algorithm SELENA (Molina et al. 2010) has been adapted to allow for the computation of a time-dependent loss curve employing the time-dependent hazard curve obtained for the city of Hveragerði. Additionally, the residential buildings within the municipality have been classified into three main typologies and the vulnerability functions proposed by Bessonon et al. (2020), correlating PGA with different damage states, have been applied.

The loss curves are obtained for the seismic series that occurred from 18 June 2000 to 24 June 2000 (just after the 17 June Mw 6.4 earthquake). The results demonstrate that the building typologies show less damage when compared with similar buildings in Europe. Masonry buildings have the highest vulnerability, timber typologies are the least vulnerable and concrete buildings are roughly in the middle. The same observation as for the seismic hazard curve can be made: the time-dependent loss curves are higher during this seismic series and the conventional loss curve represents a lower bound.

Finally, a simplified human loss model is defined to estimate injuries and fatalities to the population. Assuming three possible values for the cost of evacuation of populations from their buildings (\$20, \$50 and \$500 p.p.p.d – per person per day) and the value of human life as \$1 000 000, a simplified cost-benefit analysis has allowed us to determine that for masonry buildings the mitigation action of evacuation is only cost-beneficial for the first and second day if its cost is \$50, but it is not cost-beneficial if a cost of \$500 p.p.p.d is assumed. On the other hand, the evacuation from concrete buildings is not cost-beneficial even if the cost of evacuation is the minimum one (i.e. \$20 p.p.p.d). Therefore, we can conclude that mitigation actions should always be focused on the weakest building typologies.

2 INTRODUCTION

The path to Short-Term time-dependent Seismic Hazard Analysis (STSHA) is based on long-term input models usually expressed as ground motion prediction models, site effects, seismic source zonation, and elements at risk (the sites where the probabilistic seismic hazard analysis, PSHA, is computed). Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF) based on STSHA considers the possible short-term changes in the seismicity around the site of interest and if possible, any non-seismic information (for example radon emissions) that can also be correlated with the changes in the seismic activity. Then both kinds of information can be combined to improve the STSHA.

Figure 1 summarizes the methodological concept followed in this task, which is described in this report. The interconnections between task 3.2 and other tasks within work package 3 are also shown in Figure 1. In the proposed approach, the seismicity at a given time t_i (averaged over an appropriate forecast interval) is updated with the data coming from sensors. Aftershock forecasting models following a mainshock are investigated through the Reasenberg and Jones (1989) approach and ETAS seismicity model (Ogata, 1988). The ETAS forecast model allows allocating spatial short-term seismicity to the seismic source, which also can be incorporated with the non-seismic information models. A logic tree is proposed to assess the uncertainties not only of the long-term models but also the short-term models (seismic and non-seismic updating of the activity rates in the seismic sources). Subsequently, the PSHA forecast is computed on a daily basis after the mainshock and the hazard curves and probability gains are obtained. Although it was not initially planned in this task, but being aware of the need of recommending mitigation actions within OEF, a first approach towards cost-benefit analysis based on a risk assessment (in terms of a fatalities-risk curve) is also proposed. Here, the evacuation of the population from a given model building type is tested as a starting point that can be later improved in other TURNkey tasks. Finally, the proposed methodology fulfils the goal of the task by providing a hybrid methodology that can be easily updated in the future and a logic tree that can be easily modified to consider additional uncertainties.

The deliverable is structured as follow. Section 3 explains the methodology used in the different approaches. Section 4 carries out the application of the proposed methodology to Testbed 3 and 4 and obtains the model between the radon measurement and the increase in the daily seismic activity rates for Vrancea region (Romania). Finally, Section 5 shows the time dependent loss model computed for Testbed 3 and how evacuation mitigation actions may be considered through a simplified cost-benefit analysis.

The current deliverable is divided into a main report and an appendix volume. In addition, Deliverable 3.5 summarize the developed algorithm.

Fixed at first but potentially updated using inputs from testbeds, Tasks 3.4 + 3.5 + 5.3 + WP4

Figure 1. Proposed approach (concept) to develop an improved procedure for OEF.

3 METHODOLOGY FOR AN IMPROVED PROCEDURE ON OEF

3.1 Methodology of ETAS forecasting model to be integrated in the OEF system of the TURNKEY platform

3.1.1 Introduction

ETAS (Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequences) seismicity model is used widely for short-term operational earthquake forecasting (OEF), in particular after a large event. This model has been implemented within the TURNkey platform for the purpose of development of an operational system for computing the short-term seismicity forecasts. The ETAS model provides us with spatial earthquake occurrence rates for magnitude larger than a defined threshold for a specific forecasting time interval. The short-term forecasting time window can range from hours to weeks. In order to obtain short-term hazard values, the resultant short-term seismicity rates from ETAS is exploited within the seismic hazard assessment framework. As the final main product of the OEF system, the short-term probability of exceedance from the threshold PGA and spectral values is generated for the target region.

Iceland is recognized as a land of natural hazards and intense seismic and volcanic activity. The multiple monitoring networks of various geophysical markers and the availability of detailed earthquake catalogues complete down to small earthquake magnitudes make this testbed (i.e. TB3) an ideal test region in the TURNkey project for exploring the feasibility and limits of OEF.

To this end, we retrospectively provide seismicity forecasts of the spatial distribution of events within a prescribed forecasting time window during the June 2000 aftershock sequence in the South Iceland Seismic Zone (SISZ) using a fully simulation-based procedure. The method is based on a well-established Bayesian spatio-temporal ETAS model which enables estimation of the model parameters

for earthquake occurrence while accounting for their uncertainties in a robust manner through posterior joint probability distributions. Subsequently, we estimate the short-term seismic hazard values at the testbed locality of Hveragerði-town in the SISZ and compare the results with the seismic hazard values obtained from a conventional probabilistic seismic hazard assessment (i.e., long-term).

3.1.2 Seismicity forecasting models

On short time scales less than a few months, earthquake sequences show a high degree of clustering in space and time. The probability of triggering increases with the initial shock's magnitude and decays with elapsed time according to simple scaling laws. The first generation of models used to describe short-term clustering of earthquakes are the Omori law (Omori 1894), Omori-Utsu law (Omori, 1894; Utsu, 1961; Utsu and Ogata, 1995) also known as modified Omori law), and Reasenberg and Jones (1989). ETAS (Epidemic-Type Aftershock Sequences) is a space-time-magnitude forecasting model introduced by Ogata (1988) that provides improved forecasts over short-terms. According to several studies (e.g. Marzocchi and Lombardi 2009; Nandan et al. 2017; Schorlemmer et al. 2018; Taroni et al. 2018), the ETAS model ranks top among the best models of earthquake forecasting developed to date and it outperforms several published models (e.g. physics-based and statistical models). Contrary to Omori-Utsu and Reasenberg and Jones (1989), the ETAS model takes into account the effect of secondary aftershock sequences (i.e. sequences with large aftershocks that trigger their own aftershocks). In the ETAS model, any earthquake irrespective of its size may trigger other earthquakes, which in turn may trigger more earthquakes, leading to a cascade of triggering. In other words, within the ETAS model, every earthquake is regarded as both triggered by earlier events and as potential trigger for subsequent earthquakes. Furthermore, it may forecast the evolution of complex seismic sequences (e.g. the 2016-2017 Amatrice-Norcia sequence) (Ebrahimian and Jalayer, 2017; Marzocchi et al., 2017).

3.1.3 Spatio-Temporal ETAS model

There is large estimation uncertainty in the parameters of the ETAS model because of the incomplete data in low seismic areas due to detection and recording problems and also in early aftershocks period. Several ETAS model parameters estimation techniques employ only the best parameter values, therefore estimation error increases noticeably and consequently leads to poor forecasting after a large mainshock (Ross 2016). Furthermore, Lombardi (2017) performed uncertainty analyses on ETAS models and corroborates that the epistemic uncertainty of ETAS-type models is much lower than the aleatory variability of the process. She shows that an experienced analyst is likely to set the ETAS-type models, however, the seismicity forecasts might be determined with limited accuracy and precision, in particular through retrospective studies (Lombardi 2017). Therefore, special attention should be paid to the uncertainty of the ETAS parameters.

For that reason, we apply a Bayesian spatio-temporal ETAS model which is capable of quantifying ETAS model parameter uncertainties. Hence, investigating a limited number of Bayesian-based ETAS models (please refer to the Deliverable 3.1-Part1), we came to the conclusion that the model proposed by Ebrahimian and Jalayer (2017) that showed promising results for the 2016 Amatrice seismic sequence in central Italy is most suitable for the future OEF system to be implemented within the TURNkey platform. One of the strong features of the selected approach is the robust forecast not only capturing uncertainty in the parameter estimates for the sequence of events that occurred before the forecasting interval, but also simulating the sequence of events within the prescribed forecasting time interval, in addition to providing a spatio-dependent seismicity forecast.

3.1.3.1 Model Description

Following is a description of the spatiotemporal ETAS model for robust seismicity forecasting based on the Bayesian parameter estimation technique. Herein, the spatiotemporal seismicity forecast is known as the earthquake occurrence rate for a specific magnitude threshold at time t elapsed after the beginning of the selected seismic sequence (which mostly agrees with the origin time of the mainshock) within a forecasting time interval that is distributed spatially across the affected region.

Figure 2. Schematic sketch of the seismicity forecasting framework using a sequence-based Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model

Figure 2 indicates a schematic sketch of the sequence-based Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS forecasting model. The expected number of earthquakes (denoted as N) derived from ETAS model is calculated using Eq. 1 based on two terms shown on the right side of Eq. 1. The first term is the background seismicity (N_b) which is usually considered to be time-independent and presents long-term seismicity. The second term is the triggering function which determines the rate of occurrence of events with potential of triggering offspring of its own during the forecasting interval $[T_{start}, T_{end}]$ (denoted as λ in Eq. 1).

$$N(x, y, m | seq, M_l) = N_b(x, y, m | M_l) + \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\int_{\Omega_\theta} \left[\int_{\Omega_{seq}} \int_{T_{end}}^{T_{start}} (\lambda(t, x, y, m | seq_g, \theta, seq, M_l)) dt \right] \cdot p(seq_g | \theta, seq, M_l) dseq_g \cdot p(\theta | seq, M_l) d\theta$$

$N(x, y, m | seq, M_l)$ is the expected number of events in the spatial cell unit (x, y) with $M \geq m$ in the forecasting interval $[T_{start}, T_{end}]$ given seq and the lower cut-off magnitude M_l . seq is the observation history of events in the interval $[T_o, T_{start})$ before the beginning of the forecasting interval. The ETAS model is applied to the most recent earthquake sequence, which includes all triggered earthquakes with magnitude greater than a lower cut-off magnitude (M_l). Therefore, either the previous sequence or the long-term seismicity rate can be added as background seismicity and the beginning of the ongoing sequence is re-defined when a new sequence starts. Note that M_l is defined as the magnitude of completeness of the catalogue. $p(\theta | seq, M_l)$ is the conditional probability distribution function (PDF) for ETAS model parameters (θ) given seq and M_l . $p(seq_g | \theta, seq, M_l)$ is the PDF for the

sequence of events generated within the forecasting interval (denoted as seq_g), given θ and seq (see Eq.2).

As indicated in Eq.2, the spatiotemporal ETAS triggering function consists of three main functions: 1) the magnitude-dependent aftershock productivity associated with the Gutenberg-Richter relationship, 2) the temporal decay of aftershocks defined by the modified Omori's law, 3) the spatial decay of aftershocks relative to the epicentre of the parent event:

$$\lambda_{ETAS}(t, x, y, m|\theta, seq_t, M_l) = e^{-\beta(m-M_l)} \sum_{t_j < t} K_t \cdot e^{\beta(M_j - M_l)} \cdot \frac{K_t}{(t - t_j + c)^p} \cdot \frac{K_R}{(r_j^2 + d^2)^q} \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

The ETAS model parameters, denoted as θ , include a vector comprising β , c , p , d , and q as shown in Eq.2. Note that K , K_t , K_R are defined as functions of θ (see Ebrahimian and Jalayer, 2017). In order to generate samples of θ from the probability distribution of $p(\theta|seq, M_l)$, a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulation routine (Jalayer and Ebrahimian, 2014; Beck and Au, 2002) based on a Metropolis-Hastings (MH) algorithm (Metropolis et al., 1953; Hastings 1970) is employed. $p(\theta|seq, M_l)$ is computed using a Bayesian approach and a lognormal distribution is considered as prior information for each of the parameters (β , c , p , d , q) with a coefficient of variation of 0.3. To generate daily forecasts, the ETAS parameters are updated and their corresponding statistics, i.e. mean and coefficient of variation (CV), are reported on a daily basis. The first few samples during an initial transition time are often thrown out and after accumulating a sufficient number of events, the model reflects samples from $p(\theta|seq, M_l)$.

In order to generate a seq_g (i.e. ongoing aftershock sequence generated within the forecasting interval) given the sampled values of θ , seq and M_l , a stochastic procedure is adopted according to Ebrahimian and Jalayer (2017). The probability distribution $p(seq_g|\theta, seq, M_l)$ is given by Eq. 3 as follows:

$$p(seq_g|\theta, seq, M_l) = \prod_i p(IAT_i, x_i, y, M_i|seq_{g_{i-1}}, \theta, seq, M_l) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where $seq_{g_i} = \{seq_{g_{i-1}}, (IAT_i, x_i, y, M_i)\}$ and $IAT_i = t_i - t_{i-1}$ stands for inter-arrival time for the i th event and implies the time between two consecutive events.

Finally, a robust estimate for the number of events with $M \geq m$ in a spatial cell centred at (x, y) within the aftershock zone considering the uncertainties in the spatiotemporal distribution of the sequence of events, denoted as $N(x, y, m|seq, M_l)$, can be determined from Eq. 1. For a more detailed description, please refer to Ebrahimian and Jalayer (2017).

3.1.3.2 Required inputs for applying the Bayesian ETAS model

Earthquake catalogue

The most important input is an earthquake catalogue including latitude, longitude, origin date and time, moment magnitude of all events in a specific seismic sequence that occurred in the target region or a defined aftershock zone. The seismic sequence catalogue is comprised of both mainshocks and dependent shocks (i.e. foreshocks and aftershocks).

Aftershock zone

The target region is a zone covering the geographical distribution of the seismic sequence under study. The aftershock zone is assumed to be rectangular and therefore, defined by latitude and longitude of upper right and lower left corners. If the spatial extension of the triggered events within a specific earthquake sequence changes (i.e. after inspection of aftershocks collected within the next hours, days or weeks), the aftershock zone needs to be re-sized to cover the whole affected area. The region is divided into uniform square-shaped grid cells. The cell size is defined by the user. The default value for Iceland is $0.0227^\circ \times 0.01^\circ$. The short-term seismicity rates for various magnitude thresholds are estimated for each grid cell using the spatiotemporal ETAS model.

Magnitude of completeness

The magnitude of completeness (M_c) defines the completeness threshold of the earthquake catalogue. M_c should be estimated for each subsequent earthquake catalogue compatible with the forecasting intervals. The determined time-variant M_c is considered as a lower bound of seismic sequences on which the seismicity models are applied. Herein, the M_c values are calculated based on two methods. The first approach is based on the regression over the conventional magnitude-frequency distribution of observed seismic events that occurred during the learning period. In this procedure, M_c is defined following a Gutenberg-Richter relationship by fitting a linear relation to the semi-logarithmic frequency-magnitude distribution of the triggered events during a sequence corresponding to the desired forecasting interval. The second approach is based on the b-value stability approach proposed by Cao and Gao (2002) and Bayesian updating for computing the b-value against a set of magnitude thresholds. In this procedure, M_c is defined by visual inspection of the stability (invariability) of the maximum likelihood for the posterior distribution of b-value, denoted as $p(b|\text{seq}, M_l)$ in Ebrahimian et al. (2014). It should be noted that M_c tends to be higher for the early time intervals after a mainshock than the value for the subsequent time interval after collecting a sufficient number of aftershocks.

Prior information for the Bayesian ETAS model

The prior information for the five ETAS model parameters, namely B , c , p , d and q , is required for better convergence in the Bayesian inference approach. These values can be extracted from previous publications. Otherwise, a noninformative distribution can be assigned to all five parameters.

3.1.3.3 Outputs of the Bayesian ETAS model

The ETAS model is expected to generate a spatial seismicity forecast. To be more specific, for each spatial cell, the expected number of earthquakes as well as the probability of occurrence of at least one earthquake with magnitude above a certain threshold (e.g. 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0) are reported for daily or weekly time intervals.

We believe that detailed operational forecasts for the time and magnitude domain with their associated uncertainty are of tremendous interest to the authorities in question (e.g. civil protection organizations). In the TURNkey project, using the Bayesian-based model enables us to report the probability distribution of posteriors of ETAS parameters along with the MCMC statistics to validate the reliability of resultant seismicity rates. Moreover, the (logarithmic) mean value of the forecasted number of events in the whole aftershock zone plus/minus one and two (logarithmic) standard deviations, i.e. the 84% and 98% confidence intervals, are reported automatically.

3.1.4 An Incremental updating of prior parameters for ETAS algorithm

A new approach has been developed here in order to estimate a set of reasonable θ for ETAS inputs to start the forecast algorithm. This algorithm is applied to TB4, and the results are illustrated in Section 4.2.

By recalling from Eq. 2, the aftershock sequence is defined as a non-homogeneous Poisson point process in space and time. Therefore, the aftershock zone is defined as the set A in the Cartesian space discretized into subsets, which represent spatial cells centred at $(x, y) \in A$. The event rate of occurrence in the forecast interval $[T_{\text{start}}, T_{\text{end}}]$ at time t after the mainshock occurred at the origin time T_0 with a magnitude greater than or equal to m (less than the lower cut-off magnitude M_l) and in the cell unit (x, y) can be expressed by $\lambda(t, x, y, m | \theta, \text{seq}, M_l)$ as written in Eq. 2. $\text{seq}_t = \{(t_j, x_j, y_j, M_j), t_j < t, M_j \geq M_l, j = 1: N_0\}$ is the observation history up to the time t consisting of N_0 events (including mainshock and the sequence of aftershocks) that have taken place before the forecast interval $[T_0, T_{\text{start}}]$; parameter β is related to the Gutenberg-Richter seismicity; parameters c and p are similar to those of the Modified Omori's Law defining the decay in time of short-term triggering effects; d and q characterize the spatial distribution of the triggered events; r_j is the distance between the location (x, y) and the epicentre of the j^{th} event (x_j, y_j) ; parameters K , K_t and K_R satisfy the achievement of asymptotic compatibility between ETAS forecasts and the long-term seismicity. Hence, the vector of ETAS model parameters can be defined as $\theta = [\beta, K, K_t, K_R, c, p, d, q]$. By simplifying Eq. 1, the number of events at the centre point of a given spatial cell unit centred at (x, y) with magnitude greater than or equal to m in the forecast interval $[T_{\text{start}}, T_{\text{end}}]$ can be written as Eq. 4.

$$N(x, y, m | \text{seq}, M_l) = N_b(x, y, m | M_l) + \int_{T_{\text{start}}}^{T_{\text{end}}} \lambda(t, x, y, m | \theta, \text{seq}_t, M_l) dt \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where $N_b(x, y, m | M_l)$ is a constant representing the background seismicity of the area, and N defines a time-dependent spatial distribution for different magnitudes which can be used further for the short-term Time-Dependent Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis (TDPSHA). As can be seen in Figure 3, the proposed algorithm starts its computations ' M ' months before the forecast interval and chooses several subsets of ' E ' events greater than or equal to the magnitude of completeness. A non-informative prior ($b=1, c=0.03, p=1, d=1, q=1.5$) is used for the first subset, and the MCMC algorithm is used to update these values based on the first subset catalogue. Subsequently, the posterior distributions of the previous subset are used as the prior distributions for the next subset. This procedure repeats until we reach the last subset, which ends before the time of the forecast. Each subset is also checked to cover at least ' D ' days of the catalogue, i.e. if E events happen in less than D days, then we increase the subset to cover at least D days of events. Additionally, we check that all the events within a specific day are being selected in a subset, i.e. no subset ends at the middle of a sequence on a specific day.

This proposed algorithm ensures that the final prior (θ) distributions for the ETAS model have been trained based on the previous ' E ' months catalogue. However, as will be discussed in the next sections, the average posterior θ over a series of sequences can also be used as a rational choice.

Figure 3. The flowchart of Incremental updating of ETAS prior parameters.

3.2 Methodology of RJ forecasting model to be integrated in the OEF system of the TURNKEY platform

Reasenber and Jones (1989) introduced a statistical model for the aftershock rate following a mainshock. They provided a set of generic parameter values for California based on the available earthquake catalogue containing previous aftershock sequences. The proposed model is based on Eq. 5, which combines the modified Omori decay of aftershocks (Utsu 1957), the Gutenberg-Richter magnitude-frequency distribution (Gutenberg and Richter 1944), and the Utsu aftershock productivity (Utsu 1972):

$$\lambda(t, M) = 10^{a+b(M_m-M)}(t+c)^{-p} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where $\lambda(t, M)$ is the rate of events with magnitudes greater than M at time t following a mainshock of magnitude M_m , b is the b-value of the magnitude-frequency distribution, a is the aftershock productivity parameter, p is a parameter describing the temporal decay of the sequence, and c denotes the period of time before the beginning of the temporal decay.

Hardebeck et al. (2019) updated the Reasenber and Jones parameters for different regions in California based on the available catalogue between 1980 and 2017. They found lower aftershock productivity values than those reported by Reasenber and Jones. This was due to considering a larger number of sequences exhibiting low seismicity in their study than were included in the original calculations by Reasenber and Jones. These updated generic parameters can be employed at the initiation of a new sequence and can be updated by Bayesian approaches as the sequence progresses, i.e. to sequence-specific aftershock parameters. However, we need to define a reliability or an efficiency index to assess the ongoing updating of the sequence-specific aftershock parameters, otherwise using the generic parameters is preferable. A consistent approach has been discussed as well for the spatially modified Omori model by Ebrahimian et al. (2014). However, they concluded that the epidemiological type of spatio-temporal aftershock clustering model is superior.

Testbed 4 (Patras and Aegio region in Greece) is considered here as the case study for deriving the aftershock parameters by implementing the Reasenber and Jones (1989) model. The earthquake catalogue is gathered from the International Seismological Centre (ISC)¹ database. Other catalogues were not used since for example, the National Observatory of Athens² (NOA) network became digital only after 2000. In Greece, there are two institutions reporting phases (bulletin data) to ISC: NOA and Aristotle University of Thessaloniki³ (AUTH). In other words, there is no common bulletin for Greece, although, since 2007, there is a unified network sharing waveform data with the public. NOA is the official seismic monitoring agent in Greece; however, ISC reports a few small earthquakes not contained in NOA's catalogue using data from AUTH (very local events in northern Greece). Therefore, the ISC catalogue is the best choice for the current study.

The catalogue is rich in events with magnitudes greater than 5; however, it suffers from a lack of very low magnitudes. The small number of existing analogue stations in the regional seismic monitoring network means that the magnitude of completeness (M_c) is around 3.0 to 4.0, which indicates the need to expand the available recording network in order to increase forecasting capabilities.

¹ International Seismological Centre (2019), On-line Bulletin, <https://doi.org/10.31905/D808B830>

² <http://www.noa.gr/index.php?lang=en>

³ <https://www.auth.gr/en/uni>

The study region is defined as 21E to 23E and 37.5N to 39N. The mainshocks are defined as any event with a moment magnitude greater than 5. Aftershocks are defined as those events occurring during a ten-day period after the mainshock (to avoid considering the background seismicity) and within a 50 km distance. Any aftershock sequence with fewer than 30 events is eliminated. The magnitude of completeness is calculated for each sequence on a daily basis (Woessner and Wiemer 2005), and the aftershock parameters are calculated using the maximum-likelihood method (Ogata 1983) and a Bayesian updating approach (Ebrahimian et al. 2014).

This proposed framework can be used further to establish a real-time system for automatic aftershock forecasting (Omi et al. 2019). Omi et al. (2019) tested a prototype of a real-time system for automatic aftershock forecasting in Japan by the implementation of real-time seismicity data from the High Sensitivity Seismogram Network (Hi-net) catalogue of the National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience (NIED). Their platform starts computations three hours after a mainshock and provides forecasts on an hourly basis. It is worth emphasising that the current work will be verified by a retrospective study of the available previous seismic sequences between 1980 to 2007. Subsequently, the obtained prior parameters are tested for the sequences after 2007.

3.3 Methodology of the short-term seismic hazard model to be integrated into the OEF system of the TURNKEY platform

The 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model (ESHM13) is used in this study (Giardini et al. 2013; Woessner et al. 2015). Also, the Kernel-smoothed stochastic rate model considering seismicity and fault moment release (SEIFA-model) is employed in order to define the seismicity rate in each grid cell in the aftershock zone. First, a conventional PSHA has been performed using the following equation (Cornell 1968; McGuire 1995):

$$\lambda(PGA > pga) = \sum_{source} \lambda(M > Mmin) \int_{Mmin}^{Mmax} \int_0^{rmax} P(PGA > pga|m, r) \cdot f_M(m) \cdot f_R(r) \cdot dm \cdot dr \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where $Mmin$ is equal to 4.5 (the same assumption as in ESHM13), and $Mmax$ is assumed as the maximum magnitude. $\lambda(PGA > pga)$ is the annual rate of exceedance of PGA for a threshold peak ground acceleration. $\lambda(M > Mmin)$ is the annual rate of exceedance of earthquakes greater than $Mmin$, which is numerically defined for each grid cell based on the ESHM13 SEIFA model. $P(PGA > pga|m, r)$ is calculated based on two ground motion prediction equations (GMPEs), i.e. the one from Chiou and Youngs (2014) with a weight of 70% and the one from Zhao et al. (2006) with a weight of 30%. The 2008 version of Chiou and Youngs' GMPE has been used in ESHM13; however, we decided to use the newer version from 2014. The higher weight for the Chiou and Youngs (2014) GMPE is motivated by the high stability of this model (Bommer and Stafford 2020). $f_M(m)$ is the probability density function of magnitude, which follows the Gutenberg-Richter relationship based on the ESHM13 for each area source. $f_R(r)$ is the probability density function of distance.

The short-term (daily) time-dependent seismic hazard analysis is performed by substituting the $\lambda(M > Mmin)$ term in the previous equation by the rate obtained from the employed ETAS model. The rest of the parameters are at the same definition and values as were used for the background (time-independent) hazard calculations.

3.4 Methodology of integration of observed change in non-seismic variables in the OEF system of the TURNKEY platform

3.4.1 Introduction

A seismic precursor is a phenomenon that takes place prior to the occurrence of an earthquake. The precursors are of various kind and are classified as seismic (anomalous seismicity and microseismicity, swarms and foreshocks, changes in b-value, hypocentral migration, changes in released energy and seismic waves velocities) and non-seismic precursors, like geophysical/geochemical precursors (GP/GC P). Geophysical precursors (GP P) can be electromagnetic field variations, ground resistivity, telluric currents, ground deformation, and crustal movements, tilt and strain and in earth tidal strain, water level changes, while geochemical precursors (GC P) are radon and other gases emissions and chemical composition of underground water. These anomalous phenomena do not provide the basis for prediction of the three main parameters of an earthquake: place and time of occurrence and magnitude of the future seismic event but can forecast an increased probability of an imminent large earthquake occurrence.

According to Cicerone et al. (2009) there are two criteria for the selection of the most useful non-seismic earthquake precursor:

(i) The first criterion used for the selection of the earthquake precursory fields was the existing literature and reported credible scientific evidence for anomalies in the observation prior to some earthquakes. The successful measurement of some anomalous phenomena prior to an earthquake depends on the existence of a good GP/GC network operating in an area before, during, and after an earthquake. Even if there are many cases when people have reported unusual phenomena before earthquakes, like unusual clouds, smells, sounds, or animal behaviour, they cannot be used in this study because these have not been recorded or documented scientifically in a quantitative way. In order to best summarize the behaviour of precursory phenomena of interest, we have used only studies from the published scientific literature that report recorded observations of earthquake precursors observed in scientific, controlled, calibrated experiments.

(ii) The second criterion for the selection of the earthquake precursors is that there are accepted physical models to explain the existence of the precursor. For example, it only makes sense to look for changes in the local electric or magnetic field near an earthquake epicenter if there is some physical or chemical reason why the time prior to the initiation of an earthquake rupture should be accompanied by those field changes. In some cases, there are multiple, competing models to explain the existence of a reported earthquake precursor.

• Geomagnetic field

By analysing the types of geomagnetic variations that premeditate or accompany seismic events, we can draw the following conclusions:

a) Geomagnetic changes with small periods occurring in the ELF (3-30Hz), ULF (300-3000Hz), VLF(3-30kHz) range occur a shorter time before an earthquake occurs but may persist after it has occurred. Hence, a good correlation between the occurrence of these pulses and the accumulation of stress, which is lost after the stress has been released can be observed (Fenoglio et al. 1995). These types of variations can be ideal precursors to earthquakes, but unfortunately, they can very easily coincide with other disruptive phenomena of a different nature: weather phenomena, magneto-chemical phenomena, and anthropogenic activities.

b) Long-term geomagnetic variations are based on physical processes affecting the lithosphere of the Earth and are not fully understood. Freund (2003) interpreted the variation in geomagnetic field precursors to the Taiwanese Chi-Chi earthquake as being generated by electrical currents on the fault plane. Liu et al. (2006) and Yen et al. (2004) interpreted these anomalies as being due to accumulation and stress releases. This changes the conductive properties of water-saturated rocks that have been compressed or dilated due to stress, which can disturb the surface-measured geomagnetic field.

• Surface deformations

Rikitake (1976) reported that changes in ground elevations over distances of tens of kilometres have preceded some strong earthquakes. Unfortunately, observed geodetic movements are mostly co-seismic and post-seismic, and very rarely crustal deformations have been observed before major earthquakes. Geodetic measurements were used in many geophysical studies but mostly to measure co-seismic, post-seismic, and inter-seismic deformation, volcano deformation, plate motion, and crustal deformation at plate boundaries. This type of deformation takes place over a long period and involves a huge volume of data. The short-term changes in geodetic deformations before significant earthquakes are poorly studied globally, while long-term changes in geodetic deformation have more reliable results, and less uncertainties.

• Water level, temperature, and composition changes

Well-water level change is one of the most reported earthquake precursors. Changes in groundwater levels have been observed before certain earthquakes (Martinelli 2000) and are believed to be in response to volumetric strain in the earth's crust. However, in order to determine the groundwater level changes directly related to crustal strain, nontectonic causes of water level changes must be considered. These include barometric pressure changes, tidal effects, rainfall, and extraction of groundwater and other fluids such as oil and gas.

Well-water temperature changes have also been reported prior to earthquakes. These may involve changes in the circulation patterns of groundwater bringing water of different temperatures to the surface. However, there have been relatively few reported observations of temperature changes in the ground prior to earthquakes. This is probably due to a lack of experiments to look for such an effect. The thermal conductivity of rock is quite low, and it takes many years for a significant temperature change to diffuse just a few meters in rocks. Thus, from a theoretical point of view, one would not expect to observe thermal anomalies in rocks prior to earthquakes.

Well-water composition changes are due to the emission of various gases from the earth that affect the water composition and will be part of the next chapter on radon and other gas emissions from the earth.

• Radon and other gases emissions

The radon and other gases emissions from the earth prior to earthquakes present great interest in the scientific community working in earthquake precursors because radon has been found to be responsible for many other fields' anomalous behaviour. In the next chapter, we will focus on the study of this particular phenomenon, both because it is the most documented one, but also because most Romania have a radon network integrated within the European Plate Observing System (EPOS <https://www.ics-c.epos-eu.org/>).

A more detailed review of the geophysical fields mentioned above, i.e. the geomagnetic field, the crustal deformation, and well water characteristics is found in Cicerone et al. (2009).

3.4.2 Radon anomalies (and other gases) as seismic precursors. Literature review

The release of radon from natural minerals has been known since the 1920s (Spitsyn 1926) but its monitoring has more recently been used as a possible tool for earthquake prediction because the distribution of soil-gas radon concentration is closely related to the geological structure, fracture, nature of rocks and distribution of sources. Surveying of radon concentration is not used only in earthquake forecast but also in fracture trace and environment monitoring, and is the subject of many environmental programs, especially because radon is considered a natural hazard and the main contributor to lung cancer second to smoking. Earthquake forecasts should “benefit” from the existence of radon monitoring networks all over the world, even if their main purpose is different from the seismic one.

Many researchers rely on different precursor phenomena on the Radon release from the rocks during the pre-earthquake process, because as stresses in the source region build-up, a halo of pervasive microfracturing spreads outward through the crust, allowing radon gas trapped in uranium- and radium-bearing rocks to escape and percolate upward through rocks and soil. For instance, the pre-earthquake thermal infrared (TIR) anomalies, based on CO₂ emanation leading to a local greenhouse effect or latent heat due to condensation of water on air ions is formed as the result of anomalous radon emanation (Pulinets et al. 1997; Ouzounov et al. 2011). Perturbations in the ionosphere are related to changes in the conductivity of the near-ground air, primarily due to radon emanation. The idea that radon gas would emanate from the ground in large quantities to significantly ionize the air has been widely used to explain pre-earthquake ionospheric perturbations (Pulinets and Boyarchuk 2005; Pulinets et al. 2007, 2015).

What happens underground some minutes or hours or even several months before an earthquake is unknown exactly and up to now, there are many difficulties in deciphering and understanding the physics of pre-earthquakes phenomena. Therefore, in order to evaluate precursory phenomena properly and to be able to use them confidently for predictive or probabilistic purposes, one has to understand the physical processes that might give rise to them.

The main radon isotope ²²²Rn in groundwater and near-surface air is generated by the alpha decay of the radium isotope ²²⁶Ra as part of the uranium decay chain (Freund 2011). ²²²Rn has a half-life of 3.8 days. Changes in the rate, at which ²²²Rn are released, have been repeatedly reported prior to major earthquakes (Hauksson and Goddard 1981; Igarashi et al. 1995; Chaudhuri et al. 2011). Sustained radon monitoring programs have been in operation since the early 1970s in China around Beijing and in provinces such as Hopeh, Liaoning, Szechwan, and Yunnan (Anonymous 1977; Wakita et al. 1980; Liu et al. 1983; Wang et al. 1984). Both long-term and short-term radon anomalies have been observed and they have played a role in the prediction of several major earthquakes such as Haicheng (1975), Lungling (1976), and Sungpan-Pingwu (1976) (Teng 1980; Wakita et al. 1980; Wakita 1984; Sano 1988; Notsu et al. 1991; Virk and Singh 1993, 1994)

Based on radon anomalies observed before earthquakes, past researches (Hauksson and Goddard 1981; Allegri et al. 1983; Igarashi and Wakita 1990) have indicated that changes in the radon release rate may be one of the key earthquake precursory phenomena. ²²²Rn is believed to emanate from fractures in the rocks and from the soil, an inherently porous medium. However, changes in temporal and spatial radon release rates due to non-seismic activities have also been observed, indicating that radon release depends on specific rock/soil properties, especially on the local radium concentrations (Cicerone et al. 2009).

Freund (2011) points to the highly oxidizing property of stress-activated positive hole charge carriers, symbolized by h^+ , capable of spreading over large distances and passing through the soil. The h^+ may preferentially interact with radon that is expected to form—in the soil—stable bonds to carbon and it would release the radon and thereby provide for coupling between pre-seismic activity, specifically the build-up of stress deep in the Earth's crust and the release of radon from the Earth surface. The radon is transported essentially by two mechanisms: molecular diffusion and forced advection.

In general radon measurements can be performed in continuous, integrating, or discrete mode, regarding the time duration of measurement, and by using passive devices, when radon enters the detection system by natural diffusion, or active technique when gas is pumped in the device, that require electric power. The emission trend and anomalies highly depend on the type of measurements, continuously or at time intervals, in water, underground, or on the ground in the air. Some types of the most used detectors for in-soil radon measurements are the following: Solid state nuclear track detectors, Electret detector, Activated charcoal detector, Thermoluminescent detector, Scintillation detector. In the last years, active devices have been used for continuous measurements of soil radon gas. They use prevalently detectors as ionization chamber or silicon detectors. These devices have more performance respect to the previous ones because they allow continuous measurements and on-line reading by means of remote data transfer and real time monitoring of the radon temporal trend.

3.4.2.1 *Non-seismic radon anomalies*

In order to detect the radon anomalous variation prior to large earthquakes or volcanic activity, the normal pattern of activity in the radon concentration is required to be known and understood.

The normal variation of radon emissions has a daily, seasonal or annual variation and is strongly influenced by meteorological parameters, such as air/soil temperature, precipitation, rainfall, barometric pressure, wind velocity, humidity (Kobayashi et al. 2015; Morales-Simfors et al. 2020). These meteorological variables strongly contribute to changes in radon concentration (i.e. air, soil, and groundwater), which can be misinterpreted and confused as seismic anomalous radon signals.

There are several mathematical methods (e.g. the Power Spectrum Analysis, the Wavelet Analysis, Multiple Linear Regression, the Fractal Analyses) for removing the meteorological effects in the data sets (Das et al. 2006; Laiolo et al. 2012; Barman et al. 2015, 2016; Silva et al. 2015) and highlight the information that is hidden in the time-series data.

3.4.2.2 *Radon anomalies prior to earthquakes occurrence*

Most of the researchers define radon anomaly as a positive deviation that exceeds the mean radon level by more than twice the standard deviation.

Various rules to identify earthquakes relating to radon signals have been proposed by several researchers (Scholz et al. 1973; Dobrovolsky et al. 1979; Igarashi and Wakita 1990; Hartmann and Levy 2005; Nevinsky et al. 2015, 2018).

For this literature review, we have taken into account information from 81 articles from ISI web of knowledge (published between 2005 and 2020), that are presenting different methodologies used to detect radon anomalies in relation to the occurrence of large earthquakes. The methods were adapted to the devices used for radon measurements, the number of existing devices (single measurement or a monitoring network), distance from the seismogenic sources, the characteristics of the seismogenic sources (crustal, intermediate depth, faults), and also the seismic potential (maximum possible magnitude, activity rate) of the studied source.

Cicerone et al. (2009) contains the complete listing of gas emission anomalies found in the literature search before 2005 along with estimates of the initiation time, strength, and duration of the gas anomalies (see Table 2 in Cicerone et al. 2009). There is a very wide range of earthquake magnitudes for which anomalous radon precursors have been reported. The smallest earthquake magnitude is 1.5 and the largest is 7.9. Most of the observations are for earthquakes greater than magnitude 4.0. Radon gas changes up to 1200% relative to background radon concentration levels are reported although most of the changes are between 20% and 200%, with the most reported change between 50% and 100%. Besides, 83% of the observations reported that radon levels increased prior to the earthquake relative to the background radon levels.

From the studied literature, we have extracted the more used radon concentration anomalies, considered as seismic precursors:

- Changes in radon data, exceeding 2σ (σ is the standard deviation) in precursor time spread over different durations from diurnal, several days, weeks, months, seasonal, annual (Hauksson and Goddard 1981; Chaudhuri et al. 2011; Jaishi et al. 2014; Nevinsky et al. 2015, 2018; Haber et al. 2017; Singh et al. 2017; Kulali et al. 2018; Joo et al. 2019).
- Intervals of $\pm 1.0\sigma$ and $\pm 2\sigma$ deviations from the average concentration (Vizzini and Brai 2012). For instance, seasonal averages of Rn concentration were calculated for spring, summer, autumn, and winter. The periods when Rn concentration deviates by more than $\pm 1.0\sigma$, $\pm 1.5\sigma$ and $\pm 2\sigma$ from the related seasonal value are considered as Rn anomalies caused possibly by earthquake events and not by meteorological parameters (Yasuoka, Yand and Shinogi 1997; Singh et al. 1999; Singh Virk et al. 2001).
- Positive and negative deviation of radon concentration from a given average, spikes from 15% to 50% (Zmazek et al. 2005).
- The anomalies defined by (Friedmann 2012), show a rather slow change of radon concentration and can continue even over years.
- Other type of anomalies appears much faster and can be followed by a slow increase or a rather constant radon concentration or be characterized as a short peak (duration: hours to days) in the radon concentration. These peaks can be either positive or negative and are often followed by an earthquake within about ten days.
- “Splashes” from the average value of the radon concentration - increase followed by a sharp decrease.
- Daily data of radon concentrations in soil and water were replaced by Nevinsky et al. (2018) by the following values: $(A_{N+1} - A_N)$, where A_{N+1} is the measured concentration of radon on the day (N+1) and A_N is the measured concentration of radon on the previous day N. All anomalies (“splashes”) falling outside of an interval within two average deviations of the new lines of data were analysed. Most frequently, changes in radon data occurred before earthquakes in the form of increasing radon concentrations, which were followed by decreasing radon concentrations on the next day (i.e., a positive “splash” followed by a subsequent negative “splash” was considered to represent one anomaly). Only positive anomalies were observed during the simultaneous occurrence of several earthquakes.
- Spectral analysis of radon concentration data or on $A_{N+1} - A_N$ radon data: power spectra, wavelet.
- Simultaneous changes in radon concentrations in a large area obtained simultaneously from more than 20 radon stations in the Northern Caucasus (South Russia) (Tsvetkova et al. 2012) and also from water and soil radon stations around the Black Sea (Nevinsky et al. 2015, 2018). have made the analysis of the soil and water radon data and. Using daily radon data, stable daily maps of radon

“fields” or a smooth change over several days were observed. These smooth changes occurred before 95% of all earthquakes with epicenters closer than 2000 km from the borders of the research area (results were similar for water radon and for soil radon).

- In the last twenty years, there have also been developed other methods in the detection of pre-earthquake patterns based on the concepts of fractality, self-organization, and non-extensivity (Lukk et al. 1996; Eftaxias et al. 2007; Ghosh et al. 2012; Petraki et al. 2013) and based on the use of regression tree Zmazek et al. (2003, 2005).

Therefore, we have seen that the choice of the average values (annual, seasonal, monthly) is different at different researchers, and that complicates the definition of anomalies $> \sigma$ for seismological application.

3.4.3 The relationship between earthquake magnitudes, epicentral distances, and observed geophysical/geochemical anomaly.

Besides the definition of the anomaly, other problems occur related to: i) the identification of the maximum distance between the epicentre of an earthquake and the site where the anomaly of radon is observed; ii) the identification of the time between the radon anomaly and the occurrence of an earthquake of a given magnitude (precursor time); iii) the magnitude of the upcoming earthquake and the importance of the tectonic structure of the seismogenic source (Riggio and Santulin 2015).

From the reviewed papers related with correlations among radon anomaly and epicentral distance, magnitude, and precursor time, it can be found that the anomalies were studied post-event and were correlated with earthquakes with magnitudes larger than 5.0, in 89% of the studied papers. In the other 11%, the magnitude of the earthquakes following the anomalies was between 3.0 and 5.0, and in only one case a swarm occurred (Piersanti et al. 2016). From the studied literature, 50% of the papers give a correlation probability of 60% between a radon concentration anomaly and a future earthquake, 20% gives a 90% - 100% probability of occurrence, 15% did not find any correlation and 15% did not mention the correlation probability. Only Nevinsky et al. (2015), Riggio and Santulin (2015), Nevinsky et al. (2018) and Morales-Simfors et al. (2020) deal with seismic catalogues and provides correlation probabilities between detected anomalies and forecasted earthquakes with corresponding uncertainties.

The precursor time was between 2 days and 3 weeks in almost all studied papers after 2005. Only Jaishi et al. (2014) reports an anomaly 45 days before the occurrence of an earthquake with $M=6.9$ and Cicerone et al. (2009) finds an evidence of a radon emission anomaly which was detected 480 days before the occurrence of a 7.2 earthquake in China, in 1976.

The distance from the earthquake to the radon monitoring device was from inside the seismogenic source to 2000 km away. The magnitude of the predicted earthquake and the precursor time are affected by the epicentral distance.

Therefore, the main conclusions here are:

(i) Neither the start nor the end of a radon anomaly seems to be directly related to the origin time of the imminent earthquake, although often an earthquake takes place within a month of an increase in radon emission and the anomaly can continue after the event.

(ii) The largest radon anomalies are reported close the epicentres of the imminent earthquake, but the amplitude of the radon anomaly does not seem to be related with a specific earthquake or its size.

(iii) The longer the radon anomaly lasts and the longer the interim period between start of the radon anomaly and the imminent earthquake, the larger the event magnitude of the subsequent earthquake.

In the studied literature, several groups investigated the maximum distances between the epicentre of an earthquake and the site of the observed geophysical or geochemical anomaly (Riggio and Santulin 2015). Many empirical relationships or relationships based on theoretical considerations were obtained. Widely used for radon diffusion is that of Hauksson and Goddard (1981): $M \geq 2.4 \log_{10} D - 0.4$, where M is the minimum magnitude required to obtain a radon anomaly at distance D (km). The application of this relation allows making a selection of the used catalogue events and can give information on the area affected by the deformation process that precedes an earthquake of a given magnitude, defining the distance at which we can detect an anomaly attributable to a given earthquake.

Subsequently, according to Table 1, a distance $D \leq 10$ km from the radon station is needed to obtain a radon anomaly from a minimum magnitude of 2.2 ± 0.5 (mean value from all the formulas) and a distance $D \leq 70$ km from a minimum magnitude of 4.0 ± 0.3 . Also, the formulas indicate that earthquakes with a minimum magnitude of 5.6 ± 0.7 at a distance $D \leq 500$ km may be responsible of anomalies observed in the radon recordings.

Table 1: Formulas of relationships between the magnitude M and epicentral distance D taken from literature.

Authors	Formulas
(Dobrovolsky et al. 1979)	$M=2.33 \log D$
(Hauksson and Goddard 1981)	$M=2.4 \log D-0.43$
(Friedmann 1991)	$M=2.4 \log D-0.84$
(Nevinsky et al. 2015)	$M = 1.3 \log D+1.2$
(Rikitake 1987)	$M=2.6 \log D-0.87$
(Virk 1996)	$M=3.13 \log D, D \in (10;50)$
	$M=2.33 \log D, D \in (50;100)$
	$M=1.79 \log D, D \in (100;500)$
	$M=1.59 \log D, D \in (500;1250)$
(Morgounov and Malzev 2007)	$M = 2 \log D+0.54$
(Fleischer and Mogro-Campero 1985)	$M=2.08 \log D$

This may explain why it is so difficult to relate a radon anomaly with a specific earthquake. The radon recordings contain information from radon anomalies from many earthquakes in an area of influence determined by the distance D . These radon anomalies are fully recorded in the station for larger magnitudes, but they may be incomplete for lower magnitudes because many of those smaller earthquakes can be outside of the mentioned influence area.

3.4.4 Proposed methodology to use Radon emission for short-term seismic hazard analysis.

From the previous discussion on radon emissions as a seismic precursor and the current state of the art of relating geophysical anomalies with precursor time, and future event magnitudes the main conclusions are that a relationship between radon emission that allows predicting the next earthquake cannot be obtained by gathering values from the literature but should be realized on reliable own data, for a network of stations situated at different distances from the seismogenic source. The relations are source-specific and cannot be obtained from studies all over the world. Additionally, the radon

anomalies related with earthquakes are observed before the occurrence of the earthquake and they often last from days to months and even after the earthquake. Then, the radon measurement for each day includes the cumulative effect due to the seismicity in the area of influence of the recording station.

Mostly, authors try to use radon anomalies as precursors of a given future earthquake. However, we believe that this is difficult because the radon measurements are, as previously mentioned, a cumulative effect of the cumulative seismicity in the area. This cumulative radon anomaly behaviour is assumed to be similar to the Gutenberg-Richter (GR) distribution in the influence area of the station, also showing a magnitude of completeness related with the size of the area of influence and the fact that the radon anomalies due to small magnitudes at a long distance from the stations are not recorded.

Subsequently, we investigate the potential correlation between the temporal evolution of the GR parameters and the temporal evolution radon signals. Therefore, the hypothesis to develop our methodology are:

- a) The Gutenberg-Richter law establishes a linear relationship between the decimal logarithm of the activity rate (λ_m) with a threshold magnitude (M_w) and the corresponding magnitude. This means that the logarithm of the daily activity rate for different threshold magnitudes is scaled by the b-parameter and the magnitude, i.e., $\log(\lambda_m > M_1) - \log(\lambda_m > M_2) = b(M_2 - M_1)$ with $b > 0$ and $M_1 > M_2$.
- b) According to the literature, the stress-strain developed within the Earth's crust before an impending earthquake increase the radon advection and it results in anomalous changes in the radon concentration. As the size of the earthquake is related to the stress-strain state, we assume it exists a direct relationship between the size of an earthquake and the contribution of radon due to the imminent earthquake to the background radon concentration. This contribution or anomaly represents how the occurrence of the earthquake is linked to the radon emissions.
- c) Assuming this linear relationship between the magnitude of the earthquake and the radon anomalies ($R_n = c + d M_w$) where M_w will be the impending earthquake size, we assume that the decimal logarithm of the daily radon rate (λ_{R_n}) exceeding a threshold radon value (R_n) follows a similar scaling law as the Gutenberg-Richter relationship because the observed daily radon concentration is a cumulative measurement of the daily seismic activity rate. That is, it follows the relationship:

$$\log(\lambda_{R_n} > R_n) = e + f \cdot R_n$$

However, if we select an influence area large enough to consider the radon contribution from large earthquakes, the radon anomalies from many smaller earthquakes will not be recorded by the radon station, so a minimum magnitude is expected (magnitude of completeness) for radon activity) and the values e and f have to be functions of the magnitude to incorporate the scaling behaviour with the different threshold magnitudes of the seismic activity rate.

- d) Finally, a correlation is proposed between $\log(\lambda_m > M)$ and $\log(\lambda_{R_n} > R_n)$ assuming a proportionality between both variables.

These hypothesis agree with the results from Martinelli et al. (1995) who, after removing radon variations due to temperature, pointed out a possible correlation between large radon anomalies and earthquakes with $M > 2.5$. Besides, Walia et al. (2003) proposed a linear relationship between the logarithm of the radon anomaly and the magnitude of the earthquakes, and this relationship was

different according to the size of the earthquakes (one relationship for $M \leq 3.5$ and another for $M > 3.5$).

3.4.4.1 Proposed model

According to our hypothesis, the model to be correlated is:

$$\log(\lambda_m) = f_1(M_w) \cdot (\text{Rn anomaly}) + f_2(M_w)$$

In order to obtain the proposed model, two time series have to be prepared. The first one is the time history of the seismic activity rate in the region (λ_m). To do that we use the seismic catalogue for the Vrancea region in the period when radon emissions have been recorded simultaneously. The earthquake catalogue considers the seismicity within a distance (R_E) from the radon station (Papachristodoulou et al. 2020) related with the preparation zone, D (defined by Dobrovolsky et al. (1979)):

$$R_E \leq 1.5 \cdot D \leq 1.5 \cdot 10^{0.43 \cdot M}$$

The daily seismic activity is computed using the methodology proposed by Gulia et al. (2016). Following this methodology, a continuous GR parameter time series is obtained trying devoid artifacts (Tormann et al. 2013; Kamer and Hiemer 2013). A fixed number of events (100 events) is chosen and they are moved through the catalogue event by event, thus exploring the full range of variability in the data Gulia et al. (2016). The correct assessment of the completeness magnitude M_c is critical for the correct estimation of the GR parameters, therefore the maximum curvature method as suggested by (Tormann et al. 2013) is used. The GR parameters are usually plotted at the beginning, middle, or end of the time window that they represent. Following Tormann et al. (2013), the values are assigned to the end of the time window as it is the most sensible to physically understand the resolved signals.

The software ZMAP (Wiemer 2001; Wiemer and Wyss 2002) is used for computing the temporal evolution of the seismic activity. Finally, once the temporal evolution of a and b are obtained, those values allows to compute the temporal evolution of the daily activity rate with a threshold magnitude (λ_m).

The second one is the time history of radon measurements (Rn anomaly). Piersanti et al. (2015), Kobayashi et al. (2015) and Papachristodoulou et al. (2020) pointed out the importance of removing meteorological parameters as the temperature that can feature an annual and monthly seasonality on the radon temporal series. Besides, other non-seismic parameters that can influence the radon temporal series can be filtered using a linear trend removal. Finally, a moving average filter on the radon signal has to be applied before any correlation with the seismicity. Piersanti et al. (2015) indicates that 15 days moving average filter provides better results when compared with 3, 7 and 10 days.

Our model does not provide the probability of a precursor but the daily seismic activity rate increase from the radon measurement. Subsequently, the seismic activity rate can be included into a PSHA logic tree where a branch represents the computation of this parameter using seismic methods and other branch using non-seismic methods (radon).

Taking into consideration that the correlation between the non-seismic information and the activity rate is a very novel methodology, the highest weight is given to the seismic activity computed using conventional methods and the lowest weight is given to the activity rate computed using non-seismic

information. Anyway, the weights can be adapted for each testbed depending on the quantity and quality of radon data (more information is developed in section 4.2.5).

For regions without any radon information, the non-seismic branch is weighted zero and thus it is not considered in the PSHA.

3.5 Methodology of integration of time-dependent loss in the OEF system of the TURNKEY platform

3.5.1 Introduction

SELENA (SEismic Loss Estimation using a logic tree Approach) is developed by NORSAR and the University of Alicante (Molina et al. 2010) as an open-source risk and loss estimation software coded in MATLAB (The Mathworks, Inc.). The main core of the software is based on HAZUS (FEMA 2009, 2015) adapted to improve the flexibility of the user to apply it to any place in the world. Additionally, a logic tree is implemented in SELENA, which allows the user to define weighted input parameters (different earthquake scenarios, ground motion prediction equations, soil types, vulnerability files, etc.) to properly account for epistemic uncertainties.

3.5.2 SELENA methodology

Figure 4 summarizes the concept of the SELENA methodology. The user can choose between a loss analysis based on deterministic earthquakes (earthquake scenario) or a given shakemap (in terms of peak ground acceleration, PGA, and spectral acceleration, Sa). The shakemap is used when ground motion is computed outside SELENA (for example a PSHA map or a “near real-time” computed shakemap after an earthquake). For all the cases, the ground motion is expressed in terms of ground-motion prediction equation based-spectra or uniform hazard spectra.

The damage probability can, therefore, be obtained using a spectral-displacement-based method combining the spectral demand with capacity curves through the computation of the performance point. The methods implemented are CSM (Applied Technology Council 1996), MADRS and IDCM (ATC 2005), and N2 Method (Lubkowski and Duan 2001), and the damage probability in the corresponding damage states is computed through fragility curves (Eq. Eq. 7).

Additionally, the damage probability can be obtained directly from Sa fragility curves or PGA fragility curves using Eq. Eq. 7 for a given spectral demand (IM) to compute the damage states. The mathematical form for such a fragility curve is:

$$P[ds|IM] = \Phi \left(\frac{1}{\beta_{ds}} \ln \left(\frac{IM}{\bar{IM}_{d,ds}} \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

with:

IM - the intensity measurement (PGA, spectral acceleration or spectral displacement),

$\bar{IM}_{d,ds}$ - the median value of intensity measurement at which the building reaches the threshold of damage state ds with k the number of ds ($k = 1$ slight, $k = 2$ moderate, $k = 3$ extensive, $k = 4$ complete or complete with collapse),

β_{ds} - standard deviation of the natural logarithm of IM for damage state ds ,

Φ - standard normal cumulative distribution function.

Figure 4. Summary of the SELENA methodology concept.

The number of uninhabitable buildings is computed using the formula:

$$UNINH = N_4 + 0.9 N_3 + 0.5 N_2$$

where N_k corresponds to the number of residential buildings with damage state k .

Given that the building inventory is provided in terms of building floor area, SELENA may also be used to estimate the total amount of economic losses caused by the structural damage in any input currency and in any geographical unit.

The economic losses for building repair (mostly for damage states slight and moderate) and replacement (mostly for damage states extensive and complete) are computed in the following way:

$$L = \sum_{j=1}^{mbt} \sum_{k=1}^{ds} A_j P_{j,k} C_{j,k}$$

with:

ds - number of damage states k ,

mbt - number of model building types,

A_j - built area of the model building type j ,

$P_{j,k}$ - structural damage probability for the damage states k ,

$C_{j,k}$ - cost of repair or replacement (per [m²]) for different damage states k and different building type j provided in the input currency.

The mean damage ratio (MDR) formula used is:

$$MDR = \frac{1}{A_T} \sum_{i=1}^{geounits} \sum_{j=1}^{mbt} (DR_S^j A_{Si}^j + DR_M^j A_{Mi}^j + DR_E^j A_{Ei}^j + DR_C^j A_{Ci}^j)$$

with:

DR_k^j - is the damage ratio (repair / total cost) of model building type j corresponding to damage state k ,

A_{ki}^j - is the damaged built area for the model building type j in geounit (usually a district or municipality) i , corresponding to damage state k ,

A_T - is the total built area over all model building types j and all geounits i .

The number of casualties due to direct structural damage for any given structural type, level of building damage, and injury severity can be calculated by:

$$K_i^S = \{\text{injuries(severity } i)\} = \sum_{j=1}^{mbt} \sum_{k=1}^{ds} C_{i,k}^{CSR} P_{j,k} N_j^{Pop}$$

with:

$C_{i,k}^{CSR}$ - casualty rate of severity i for damage state k ,

$P_{j,k}$ - structural damage probability for the damage state k and the model building type j ,

N_j^{Pop} - number of people in the model building type j ,

mbt - number of model building types,

ds - number of damage states

3.5.3 SELENA developments for time-dependent loss analysis

SELENA was initially developed for a time-independent loss analysis. Therefore, to compute losses from a time-evolving probabilistic seismic hazard several changes were made. First, the municipality is used as the aggregation level (geounit) for the exposure, so the residential model building types and population are classified at this level. This results in a simplification of the loss analysis to render it meaningful for local authorities in coordination with civil protection as decision-makers who are responsible for the activation of the different levels of the seismic emergency protocols. However, for earthquake early warning and rapid damage estimation a more detailed distribution of ground motion, exposure distribution, and associated losses should be provided. This methodology is applied to the town of Hveragerði (Iceland) in Section 5.

3.5.3.1 Use of probabilistic seismic hazard maps for loss scenarios

As proposed by Crowley and Bommer (2006), the PSHA-based loss calculations are carried out by choosing the daily frequency of exceedances at which the loss calculations has to be computed. Subsequently, the acceleration obtained for each daily frequency of exceedance is combined with the vulnerability curves to obtain the damage probability for each damage state (slight, moderate extensive, and complete). Using multiples PSHA curves resulting from individual logic tree branches, with corresponding weights, the mean values and percentiles are obtained for the different risk metrics: number of collapsed buildings, number of uninhabitable buildings, expected economic losses (cost of repair or replacement), number of people with any injuries, and number of fatalities, associated to each exceedance rate.

3.5.3.2 Cost-benefit analysis

Deliverable D3.1 explained how a cost-benefit analysis can be carried out to support the potential operational earthquake forecasting for a given region. The increase of seismic hazard over a specific time window raises the question of whether a specific action is recommended based on the level of hazard increment and the set of potential actions. Therefore, a simple cost-benefit analysis was carried out following the methodology proposed by Van Stiphout et al. (2010).

Van Stiphout et al. (2010) carried out a demonstration study of how cost-benefit analysis may be used to allow objective risk-based decision-making. They applied the methodology to the seismic crisis of the 2009 L'Alquila earthquake using the evacuation of the population from a specific building typology as the decision to be taken. However, they found that this mitigation action is rarely cost-effective and that it may be focussed on the weakest buildings. Therefore, the methodology starts out by defining the cost, C , of a mitigation action as well as the potential loss, L . The action is favourable whenever the probabilistic risk exceeds the ratio C/L .

Additionally, deliverable D3.1 also pointed out the difficulty of obtaining accurate C and L estimates related to a mitigation action, but a first approach is to choose also the evacuation as the mitigation action and assign the values proposed by Van Stiphout et al. (2010). They consider that the cost of evacuation of a person per day was \$500 while the willingness to pay for a life saved by the government was \$1M. To perform a sensitivity analysis, the evacuation costs were assigned three different values: \$20, 50\$, and 500\$.

Section 5.1.3 describes the results obtained for the town of Hveragerði (Iceland).

4 DEVELOPMENTS OF MODELS FOR AN IMPROVED PROCEDURE ON OEF

4.1 Developed model for Hveragerði testbed (TB3): a retrospective study of the June 2000 seismic sequence using a Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model

Multiple earthquake sequences repeatedly take place in the south Iceland seismic zone (SISZ) and the Reykjanes Peninsula oblique rift (RPOR), with the largest magnitudes reaching $\sim M_w 7.0$. The capital city of Reykjavik, where about 2/3 of the Icelandic population is located, is in relatively close proximity to the seismogenic faults of RPOR. Also, various critical infrastructures such as geothermal power plants, hydropower plants and industrial companies are situated in the SISZ and RPOR regions, which make the regions to the highest seismic risk regions of Iceland.

In order to evaluate the performance of the Bayesian epidemiological type (ETAS family) spatiotemporal aftershock clustering model and to assess its applicability to a specific testbed within the TURNkey project, we carry out a retrospective forecasting experiment of the recent strong seismic sequence in the SISZ in June 2000.

4.1.1 Tectonic setting of Iceland

Iceland is the most seismically active region in northern Europe. The interplay of the mid-Atlantic ridge, an extensional plate boundary, and the Icelandic hot spot, a localized upwelling of mantle material, is responsible for the intense seismic and volcanic activity in the country. Two main major fracture zones of Iceland are the SISZ in the south, and the Tjörnes Fracture Zone (TFZ) in the north extending offshore. In south-west Iceland, three branches of the RPOR, the SISZ and the Western Volcanic Zone (a rift zone) intersect and form the Hengill Triple Junction. The SISZ is a left-lateral transform zone with E-W strike. This zone includes more than 20 parallel N-S striking faults (Figure 5) with right-lateral strike-slip motions (Einarsson 2010). The largest earthquake that struck Iceland was located in the SISZ. The Reykjanes peninsula, located west of SISZ, is an oblique extending part of the mid-Atlantic ridge with an overall strike of 70° . The highly oblique spreading leads to extensive volcanism and large earthquakes. The RPOR contains seismogenic strike-slip faults which intersect the volcanic fissure swarms. The plate movements in the area are considered capable of producing earthquakes in the magnitude range 6–6.5 with return periods of a few decades. All the strike slip N-S faults together, across the Triple Junction area, form a bookshelf fault system taking up the left-lateral component of the relative plate motion (Einarsson et al. 2020).

4.1.2 The June 2000 south Iceland earthquake sequence

At 15:40 on 17 June 2000 and at 00:51 on 21 June 2000, two of the largest events occurred within the SISZ caused by two parallel faults (Figure 5). Both faults are 15 km long, located 18 km apart. The moment magnitudes of these events are calculated to be M_w 6.4 and 6.5, respectively. The source mechanisms of both events are strike-slip based on fault plane solution. Following these large earthquakes, seismicity greatly increased in the whole southwestern Iceland, triggering 19000 microevents recorded by the SIL network and activating 90 km of the plate boundary. The triggering was attributed to dynamic processes (Antonioli et al. 2006). The mainshock was followed only a few tens of seconds later by three further large events ($M_w > 5.2$) located as far away as 80 km (Árnadóttir 2004). Note that the June 2000 double earthquakes only released one fourth of the strain accumulated across the SISZ since the major sequence of 1896–1912 (Einarsson 2014).

4.1.2.1 Earthquake catalogue

Since 1991, the digital seismic network in Iceland, SIL, operated by the Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO), recorded and detected complete earthquakes down to small magnitudes. This helped researchers to conduct detailed investigation. In the following, we use a comprehensive earthquake catalogue for the whole south Iceland assembled and revised by Panzera et al. (2016). Figure 5 shows the June 2000 earthquake sequence from 17 June 2000 to 25 June 2000 for all events with $M_w > 2.0$ occurring in the SISZ and RPOR. Earthquakes are classified by their corresponding moment magnitude as shown in the legend. The 17 June 2000 (M_w 6.4) and 21 June 2000 (M_w 6.5) earthquakes are depicted by yellow stars. The active faults are plotted based on Einarsson (2014, 2020), and Steigerwald et al. (2020) shown by black lines. SIL stations are indicated by red triangles. The pink polygon illustrates Hveragerði town, which is one of the two TB3 towns. As apparent from Figure 5, this town is located within the highly active seismic fracture zone of SISZ.

Figure 5. Geographical distribution of the June 2000 earthquake sequence in SISZ and RPOR. Hveragerði (TB3) is depicted by a pink polygon.

Figure 6 shows the temporal distribution of earthquakes with $M_w \geq 1.0$ from 17 June until 26 June 2000 taking place within the entire SISZ and RPOR (selected aftershock zone). Note that on 17 June 2000, almost no events occurred before the M_w 6.4 earthquake at 15:40:41 UTC.

Figure 6. Temporal decay distribution of the June 2000 seismic sequence

Figure 7 shows the temporal evolution of the daily number of earthquakes with magnitude 2.0 or greater (left axis) including their magnitudes (right axis). It is apparent from Figure 7 that the seismicity decays rather fast as the earthquake sequence appears to last only a few days.

Figure 7. Daily earthquake magnitudes (red circles) and daily number of earthquakes (blue circles) with $M_w \geq 2.0$

In Figure 8, the daily number of earthquakes above magnitude 2.0 for the June 2000 south Iceland seismic sequence is plotted again (left axis), while the daily cumulative number of events is represented by the red line (right axis). Earthquakes above $M_w 5.5$ that occurred during the June 2000 seismic sequence are listed with their origin date and time. More than 250 events with $M_w \geq 2.0$ happened on 17 June and more than 100 events with $M_w \geq 2.0$ happened on 18 and 21 June 2000.

Figure 8. Time evolution of the daily number of earthquakes above magnitude 2.0 (left y-axis) for the June 2000 south Iceland seismic sequence along with the daily cumulative number of events (right y-axis)

4.1.2.2 Magnitude of completeness (M_c)

In order to estimate a daily seismicity forecast, prior to applying the Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model to the earthquake sequence that is collected daily, M_c is calculated for the respective daily seq defined during the seismic sequence of interest. Hence, the desired lower cut-off magnitude, M_l , of seq for the next forecasting interval is to be greater than or equal to M_c .

Here, we adopted two approaches, a) the conventional linear regression analysis and b) the Bayesian estimation of the b-value introduced by Ebrahimian et al. (2014). The b-value maximum likelihood estimates (MLE) associated with the posterior probability distribution of $p(b|seq, M_l)$ estimated by increasing the lower cut-off magnitude (magnitude threshold) is obtained as the reliable estimates of b-value of the aftershock sequence. The magnitude threshold for which the b-value is maximum represents the M_c .

Figure 9 shows the M_c calculation for three 24-hour forecasting intervals of 18, 21 and 23 June 2000 before applying the ETAS forecasting model. The left panels represent the frequency-magnitude distribution of all triggered events with $M_w \geq 1.0$ (blue circles) that occurred from the beginning of the selected sequence until 23:59 pm on the day before the forecast. The grey line is the linear relation fitted to the observations (blue circles). The right windows of each panel illustrate b_{M_l} , the maximum likelihood estimate of the posterior distribution of $p(b|seq, M_l)$ against the magnitude threshold. M_c and M_l values are depicted by the red dashed line and dotted black vertical line, respectively. The title of each window shows its corresponding forecasting date and duration. For all daily forecasts, M_c is equal to 2.0 corresponding to the peak of b_{M_l} . Therefore, in order to reduce the computation time and effort for updating the ETAS model parameters the M_l and M_c are both set to 2.0 for the daily earthquake sequences from 17 June to 25 June 2000.

We highlight that a magnitude of completeness of 2.0 is higher than the values obtained by other researchers for the complete Icelandic earthquake catalogue, since our study is limited to the June 2000 seismic sequence. For instance, Panzera et al. (2017) applied a Bayesian magnitude of completeness (BMC) method to the SIL (Icelandic seismic network) seismic catalogue (Panzera et al. 2016) including events from 1991 to 2013 and obtained spatiotemporal measurements of M_c across the entire country. According to Panzera et al. (2017), the entire North-to-South active rift zone shows a relatively low M_c in the range of 0.5–1.0, which proves the Icelandic seismic network capability for reliable detection of small-magnitude earthquakes due to the densification of the SIL from 1991 onwards.

Godano et al. (2014) identified that the b-value is not constant but depends on a lower magnitude threshold. They observed three regimes: 1) a regime of increasing b-value for $m < M_c$, which is attributed to catalogue incompleteness. Therefore, the threshold magnitude corresponding to the maximum b-value is interpreted as the catalogue M_c . 2) a magnitude interval in which the b-value is a decreasing function of threshold magnitude followed by and 3) a subsequent slight increase for large magnitudes. Figure 9 illustrates similar attributes for the June 2000 earthquake sequence.

Figure 9. Magnitude of completeness for 24hour-forecasting intervals of 18, 21 and 23 June 2000 using two methods: conventional linear fitting (left panel) and Bayesian updating approach by Ebrahimian et al. (2014) (right panel).

4.1.2.3 Maximum magnitude, M_{max}

A maximum moment magnitude of 7.0 is expected to occur in the SISZ (Einarsson et al. 1981, Decriem et al. 2010).

4.1.3 Short-term seismicity forecasting

We generate daily spatial seismicity forecasts for the June 2000 seismic sequence using the Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model. We elaborate on the posterior distribution of ETAS model parameters and statistical tests performed to assess the reliability of the ETAS model parameters. Furthermore, we evaluate the sensitivity of various influential input variables in forecasting results such as available prior knowledge of ETAS models for the target region, number of posterior samples, grid cell size, number of Markov chains, lower cut-off magnitude (see Appendix A).

4.1.3.1 Daily seismicity forecasts after 17 June 2000

In this section, we generate spatial seismicity forecasts across the aftershock zone (SISZ and RPOR) for earthquakes with different magnitude thresholds as well as forecasted probabilities issued for 7 days starting from 18 June 2000 up to 24 June 2000 with 24-hr time forecasting window. For the sake of brevity, three forecasts maps are presented herein.

The target seismic sequence (*seq* in Eq. 1) starts from 17 June 2000 at 15:40:41 UTC, which is the origin date and time of the event with Mw 6.4. In order to issue seismicity forecasts on the next day (i.e. the desired prediction interval), all triggered events with a magnitude above a chosen lower cut-off magnitude following the abovementioned event are collected and merged into a sequence. Then, the Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model is applied to the assembled catalogue (i.e. *seq*) available at the time of issuing the forecast. Successively, for each day elapsed after 17 June 2000, the ETAS model is applied to the sequence, which consists in the collected events from the beginning of the sequence until 23:59 UTC on the day before the forecast. For instance, to provide the earthquake forecasting results for one day (24-hour time interval) on 20 June 2000, all events with magnitude above the lower cut-off magnitude, M_l , (here $M_w \geq 2.0$) that occurred since the origin time of the 17 June 2000 earthquake prior to the beginning of the forecast period, i.e. 20 June 2000 at 00:00 UTC, are assembled as the model's learning dataset (labelled as a sequence or *seq* in this study) to which the ETAS model is applied.

In order to provide a seismicity forecast, the first step is to sample values of θ (a vector of ETAS model Parameters comprised of $[\beta, c, p, d, q, K, K_R, \text{ and } K_t]$ parameters), which are generated as a Markov Chain sequence from the posterior distribution of the ETAS model parameters, $p(\theta|seq, M_l)$, conditioned on the observed earthquakes in the ongoing sequence happening before the beginning of the forecasting interval. A normal distribution with pre-defined mean value and coefficient of variation (CV) of 0.3 is assigned as prior distribution to each of the five ETAS parameters. In this study, an adaptive daily prior estimation method is applied, meaning that the mean and CV of the posterior distribution of each forecasting interval serve as prior for the subsequent forecast. The ETAS model parameters are updated daily during an ongoing seismic sequence. It should be noted that the MCMC samples of the ETAS parameters presented in this section are simulated based on 220 samplings and 5 Markov chains. Then, seq_g - simulated events that are going to take place during the forecasting interval- are generated from the probability distribution of $p(seq_g|\theta, seq, M_l)$ for the given samples of θ . To elaborate, *seq* precedes seq_g meaning that the sequence of real observations at the time when the forecast is to be issued (i.e. *seq*) precedes the generated sequence within the forecasting interval (i.e. seq_g). The method leads to a stochastic spatiotemporal distribution of

forecasted earthquakes and its corresponding uncertainty in the forecasted number of earthquakes. For detailed explanation, please refer to section 3.1.

The predicted number of earthquakes with $M_w \geq m$ (e.g. 4, 5 and 6) for the subsequent time interval, denoted as $N(x, y, m|seq, M_l)$ in Eq. 1, is calculated for each spatial cell with its centre at (x, y) and a size of $0.0227^\circ \times 0.01^\circ$. Various confidence intervals of $N(x, y, m|seq, M_l)$, namely the 2nd, 16th, 50th, 84th, and 98th percentiles, are summed over the surrounding grid cells within a radius of 2.52 km, covering an area of approx. 20 km² around each grid cell. Subsequently, the forecasted daily probabilities of having one or more earthquakes equal to or greater than m per 20 km² is calculated using Eq. 8 to map the spatial distribution of the forecasted earthquake occurrence probability. Note that in this section, the 98th percentile of the expected number of earthquakes is used to generate seismicity forecasts maps.

$$\Pr(M \geq m) = 1 - e^{-N(m|seq, M_l)} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

Figure 10 and Figure 11 display the daily forecast of seismicity for earthquakes with magnitudes above 5.5 and 6.5 for three 24-hour forecasting intervals of 18, 21 and 23 June 2000 across SISZ and RPOR. On the top, starting time and duration of each forecasting time interval is presented. The observed events with $M_w \geq 2.0$ are plotted by employing different symbols as indicated in the legend. On the left bottom side of the right panel, the daily probabilities of occurrence of at least one earthquake with magnitude greater than or equal to 4.5, 5.5, 6.5 and 7.5 are reported for the whole aftershock zone. In other words, the listed probabilities are the mean values of $N(x, y, m|seq, M_l)$ aggregated over the entire aftershock zone. The right-hand side error-bar illustrates the expected number of earthquakes with $M_w \geq 2.0$ using the median value (within the grey-filled square) plus/minus one and two standard deviations, corresponding to the interval between the 16th and 84th percentiles (black numbers) as well as 2nd and 98th percentiles (blue numbers), respectively. In addition, the number of observed earthquakes with $M_w \geq 2.0$ that occurred during the forecasting interval is shown by a red star.

The geographical distribution of the observed earthquake catalogue used as input (*seq*) for generating the daily seismicity forecasts in the right panels are depicted in the left panels.

Figure 10. Daily seismicity forecasts for earthquakes with $M_w \geq 5.5$ for 24-hr forecasting intervals of 18 June, 21 June and 23 June 2000

Figure 11. Daily seismicity forecasts for earthquakes with $M_w \geq 6.5$ for 24-hr forecasting intervals of 18 June, 21 June and 23 June 2000

Figure 12 presents the daily probability of obtaining at least one earthquake with $M_w \geq 5.5$ per 20 km². The forecast maps are generated for eight 24-hour forecasting intervals ranging from 18 June to 24 June 2000. The colour-bar shows the ranges of the forecasted probabilities. The remaining symbols are similar to Figure 11.

Figure 12. Spatial forecasts of daily probabilities of occurrence of one or several earthquakes with $M_w \geq 5.5$ per 20 km² for two 24-hour forecasting intervals of 18 and 21 June 2000

These daily probabilities increase significantly over the whole south Iceland region for aftershock sequences that immediately follow a large-magnitude ($M \geq 6.0$) event. This is apparent in the spatial seismicity forecasts of 18 June and 22 June following the 17 June (Mw6.4) and 21 June (Mw6.5) major events. The spatiotemporal ETAS model is proved to be capable of forecasting the increase in seismicity after the 17 June 2000 earthquake correctly identifying the area in which the 21 June 2000 event occurred.

4.1.3.2 Posterior statistics for ETAS model parameters

In this study, we used the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm for two main reasons, firstly to sample from the posterior distribution of $p(\theta|seq, M_1)$ as Markov Chain sequence and secondly for robust estimation of aftershock events. Table 2 presents the means and coefficients of variation (CVs) of ETAS model parameters based on MCMC simulation for 8 forecasting days from June 18 to June 24. The corresponding histograms are presented in the following section. The prior means and CVs presented in the first row of Table 2 are the initial parameters for forecasting the sequence and the priors for the subsequent days are updated on a daily basis based on the posterior distribution of the previous day. This means that we assumed that the behaviour of seismicity is learned day-by-day and informs the forecasting of the subsequent day during the ongoing aftershock sequence. Note that K , K_t and K_r parameters are determined from the first five parameters, namely β , c , p , d , and q .

Table 2: Posterior statistics for ETAS parameters based on adaptive prior procedure for seven 24-hour forecasting intervals after 17 June 2000

ETAS parameters	Initial Prior	18-June	19-June	20-June	21-June	22-June	23-June	24-June	
β	mean	1.25	0.985	1.029	1.05	1.062	1.069	1.075	1.08
	CV	0.3	0.034	0.021	0.016	0.013	0.012	0.009	0.007
c	mean	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
	CV	0.3	0.236	0.161	0.109	0.101	0.092	0.095	0.095
p	mean	1.5	1.234	1.21	1.204	1.201	1.199	1.197	1.197
	CV	0.3	0.057	0.028	0.024	0.019	0.015	0.012	0.011
d	mean	1.0	1.014	0.859	0.829	0.81	0.798	0.793	0.784
	CV	0.3	0.112	0.086	0.061	0.046	0.039	0.037	0.029
q	mean	1.5	1.581	1.605	1.602	1.604	1.603	1.602	1.604
	CV	0.3	0.036	0.021	0.017	0.014	0.013	0.011	0.01
K	mean		0.699	0.609	0.59	0.576	0.564	0.553	0.544
	CV		0.475	0.093	0.082	0.061	0.048	0.038	0.032
K_t	mean		0.065	0.068	0.069	0.069	0.069	0.068	0.068
	CV		0.115	0.033	0.025	0.021	0.018	0.019	0.018
K_r	mean		0.192	0.161	0.154	0.149	0.146	0.145	0.143
	CV		0.247	0.136	0.098	0.069	0.064	0.057	0.043

4.1.3.3 Posterior distribution of ETAS model parameters

Figure 13 illustrates sampled histograms of the posterior PDF (grey bars) and prior distribution (blue dotted lines) of six ETAS parameters (β , c , p , d , q , K), for seven 24-hour forecasting intervals elapsed after the 17 June 2000, M_w 6.4 event, a) June 18, b) June 19, c) June 20, d) June 21, e) June 22, f) June 23, and g) June 24.

4.1.3.4 Convergence diagnostic analyses for ETAS parameters on daily basis

In Figure 14, we evaluate the convergence of the MCMC algorithm by visualizing trace plots and posterior histograms of the ETAS model parameters for seven 24-hour forecasting intervals elapsed after the first large shock of the June 2000 sequence.

For five ETAS parameters, the trace plots of posterior samples obtained for the five Markov chains are colour-coded. In order to reduce the initial transient effect, the first 10% of samples during the burn-in period are discarded. The posterior histograms of five ETAS parameters are plotted using the samples corresponding to the final Markov chain (herein, chain number 5). The red solid and dashed lines show the posterior mean and posterior mean plus/minus one posterior standard deviation.

Furthermore, the convergence diagnostic analyses are based on the Gelman–Rubin statistic and autocorrelation plots. The results are plotted in the 3rd column of Figure 14. To assess the convergence of samples derived from each chain, the point estimates of the Gelman–Rubin statistic at final iterations is recommended to be below 1.05 (Gelman and Rubin 1992). Furthermore, in order to evaluate the dependency between successive samples of the Markov chains, we calculate the autocorrelation from lag 1 to 50. The panels in the right column present the autocorrelation functions for the respective parameter. The faster the autocorrelation decreases with increasing lag, the better is the effective sample size (Gelman et al. 2014). For all parameters, the degree of autocorrelations at the final lags is less than 0.1.

a) 18 June 2000

b) 19 June 2000

c) 20 June 2000

d) 21 June 2000

e) 22 June 2000

f) 23 June 2000

g) 24 June 2000

Figure 13. Posterior histograms of ETAS parameters used for daily seismicity forecasting along with the daily adaptive prior distributions (blue curves)

Figure 14. Trace plots of posterior samples of ETAS model parameters (θ) using 220 iterations and 5 chains within Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations (left) with the initial 10% of iterations during the burn-in period indicated in grey colour and the corresponding posterior histograms. On the right side of the figures, the Gelman–Rubin convergence statistics and the autocorrelation functions are depicted. The resulting convergence analyses are displayed for the forecasting interval of 21 June 2000.

4.1.3.5 Capturing uncertainty in spatial seismicity forecasts

One of the main advantages of the Bayesian estimation of ETAS model parameters is to capture uncertainty in the resultant forecasts. To illustrate their importance, we display the seismicity forecast maps for earthquakes with magnitudes above 5.5 for the 50th, 84th and 98th percentiles for the forecasting time interval on 18 June in Figure 15. The bottom left values represent the probabilities of occurrence of one earthquake with $M_w \geq 4.5, 5.5, 6.5$ and 7.5 over the whole aftershock zone.

Figure 15. Seismicity forecast maps for 50th, 84th and 98th percentiles for the 24-hours forecasting interval on the 18 June 2000 for $M_w \geq 5.5$.

According to the results, the uncertainty of the estimated number of earthquakes is quite noticeable, which highlights the importance of incorporating a Bayesian-based parameter estimation for forecasting purposes. Moreover, detailed sensitivity analyses with respect to various input variables are essential to explore the optimal values.

4.1.3.6 Seismicity forecasts for 17 June 2000

To assess the feasibility of forecasting the first large-magnitude earthquake on 17 June 2000 with M_w 6.4, we used the event catalogue from June 1998 to 16 June 2000 and run the Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model using the optimal prior values. The spatial distribution of the probability of having at least one earthquake with $M_w \geq 2.5$ per 100 km^2 is shown in Figure 16. As expected, no increase in number of events is observed due to lack of foreshocks weeks before the mainshock. Also, the aggregated probability of the occurrence of a large-magnitude earthquake is very low in the entire south of Iceland, i.e. $1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$. It should be mentioned that to gain sufficient number of events for updating of the ETAS parameters, M_l is set to 1.5. In any case, the posterior distribution of all ETAS parameters is not acceptable and shows large variability.

Figure 16. Forecasted probability of one or more earthquake with $M_w \geq 2.5$ (denoted as $M2.5^+$ in the colour-bar label) per 100 km^2 across SW-Iceland (SISZ and RPOR regions) for 24-hour forecasting intervals of 17 June 2000 (see top left text). The observed earthquakes with $M_w \geq 1.5$ occurred on 17 June 2000 are depicted by different symbols w.r.t their corresponding M_w . $Pr(M \geq 2.5, 3.5, 4.5 \text{ and } 5.5)$, listed on the bottom left side of each panel, represent the daily probabilities of at least one earthquake exceeding the defined magnitude threshold across the whole aftershock zone.

Figure 17. Daily number of earthquakes with $M_w \geq 2.0$ shown by blue circles (left-side y-axis). Note that for the sake of clear-cut manifestation, only days with more than two events are plotted. Distribution of earthquake magnitudes per day shown by red circles (right-side y-axis), the diameter of red circles is proportional to M_w . a) earthquake catalogue from June 1998 up to July 2000, b) earthquake catalogue from January up to July 2000 in logarithmic scale

In Figure 17, the daily number of earthquakes with $M_w \geq 2.0$ located in the south of Iceland are plotted by blue circles. In addition, daily earthquake magnitudes are depicted proportional to the sizes of the red circles (right-side y-axis). In order to have a detailed view of the events that occurred before 17 June 2000, a similar figure is plotted for the catalogue from 01 January 2000 until end of the June 2000 sequence. The lack of foreshocks prior to 17 June 2000 ($M_w 6.4$) is evident. By careful inspection of temporal distribution of number of earthquakes, we realize that during the 6-month time interval prior to the impending earthquake, no events with $M_w \geq 4.0$ happened. As of 01 January 2000, only one $M_w 3.9$ occurred late January and six events with $3.0 \leq M_w \leq 3.4$ happened with the latest one on 18 April 2000.

In conclusion, the retrospective study of the June 2000 earthquake sequence proved that in the absence of identifiable foreshocks, the Bayesian sequence-based ETAS model is not capable of forecasting a strong earthquake or even an elevated seismicity rate. However, due to the vast number of aftershocks in the aftermath of a large-magnitude earthquake, the sequence-based ETAS model is able to forecast the increase in the seismicity rate along with its corresponding spatial zone.

4.1.4 Short-term probabilistic seismic hazard assessment for TB3

One of the scientific outputs of the OEF system is the short-term probability of ground shaking. In this section, in order to track the elevated seismic hazard in the TB3 town in south Iceland, we perform a short-term hazard analysis. For this purpose, the number of earthquakes with magnitudes larger than M_l that occur in a specific cell of the predefined aftershock zone during a short-term forecasting time

interval is needed. In this section, the short-term spatial seismicity rates are calculated using the Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model (see previous sections) for different magnitudes ranging from 4 to 7.5.

The daily probability of ground shaking with different intensities is generated for the centre of Hveragerði town (Testbed 3). The site coordinates are 64.00°N and -21.191°W. For the hazard calculation, the distance of all cells from Hveragerði is obtained. To estimate the probability to exceed a set of specific ground shakings, GMPEs are used. A reliable selection of a set of appropriate GMPEs for each region needs a comprehensive study through data-driven ranking procedures. Since such an investigation is out of the scope, we decide to incorporate three GMPEs: 1) a local Icelandic GMPE (Kowsari et al. 2020), 2) an NGA model (Chiou and Youngs 2014) and 3) a GMPE recommended by the ESHM13 project (Zhao et al. 2006).

The daily exceedance rate is calculated by dividing the annual exceedance rate by 365. Finally, the daily probability of exceedance in Hveragerði is assessed using a Poisson distribution. For the purpose of comparing and illustrating the level of increase in hazard value, daily and annual exceedance rates are calculated using a conventional PSHA framework. Also, their corresponding probabilities of exceedance are calculated using a Poisson distribution.

Figure 18. The seismogenic zones from the area source model (AS-model) of ESHM13 for the aftershock zone of interest in south Iceland

It should be noted that to maintain consistency with other testbeds and European countries, the parameters required for PSHA calculation are extracted from the ESHM13 project. ESHM13 developed three alternative seismic source models depending on various assumptions. The area source model, called AS-model, is developed based on areal source definition. In this section, the AS-model is used to obtain seismicity parameters, faulting mechanism, maximum magnitudes, hypocentral depths, and other required parameters for conventional and short-term PSHA calculations (Woessner et al. 2015).

Figure 18 shows the seismogenic zones from the area source model developed in the ESHM13 project that apply to the south Iceland region. Below, Table 3 shows the parameters associated with the seismicity and style-of-faulting extracted from the AS-model. These parameters are obtained for all aftershock grid cells based on their attributed seismogenic zone.

Table 3: Seismic parameters associated with the source zones of AS-model

AS-model source zones	B-value	A-value	SS	NF	TF
288 - ISAS069	1	4	50	40	10
289 - ISAS070	0.8	3.4			
290 - ISAS071	0.9	3.1			
294 - ISAS075	1	3.5			

Besides the AS-model, a kernel-smoothed, zonation-free stochastic earthquake rate model considering SEismicity and accumulated FAult moment, called SEIFA-model, is used for obtaining the seismicity rate for magnitudes larger than the minimum magnitude for each cell. In the SEIFA-model, seismic activity rates are determined based on the frequency–magnitude distribution model of the SHARE European earthquake catalogue, while the spatial distribution of model rates depends on the density distributions of earthquakes and fault slip rates (Woessner et al. 2015).

4.1.4.1 Logic Tree Branches

For many hazard practitioners, various influential parameters are handled best by exploiting multiple values in a logic tree framework. Therefore, we calculate seismic hazard values based on three branching levels: 1) the ground motion prediction equations, 2) the maximum magnitude, both adopted from the AS-model, and 3) the hypocentral depth. In this regard, four different maximum magnitudes, three depths and three GMPEs are exploited in the logic tree framework employed here.

a) GMPEs:

The list of selected GMPEs and the weights assigned to their corresponding logic tree branches are as follows:

- Kowsari et al. (2020) developed for south Iceland [Kea20] with a weight of 0.5
- (Zhao et al. 2006) [Z06] with a weight of 0.4
- Chiou and Youngs (2014) [CY] with a weight of 0.1

b) Maximum magnitude:

Four values of maximum magnitude (Table 4) are considered as per AS-model with different weighting. The logic tree weights are decreasing with increasing maximum magnitude value.

Table 4: Maximum magnitude values and their associated weights proposed by the AS-model for south Iceland

	MAXMAG01	MAXMAG02	MAXMAG03	MAXMAG04
Maximum magnitude	7.4	7.6	7.8	8
Logic tree weight	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.1

c) Hypocentral depth:

The three values of hypocentral depths and their associated weights (Table 5) proposed by AS-model are defined as follows:

Table 5: Hypocentral depth values and their associated weights proposed by the AS-model for south Iceland

	HYPODEPTH1	HYPODEPTH2		HYPODEPTH3
Depth (km)	2	10		18
Logic tree weight	0.1	0.4		0.5

Note that the maximum magnitude and depth values are the same for all source zones considered in our model. In total, 36 logic tree branches are generated to capture the epistemic uncertainty in the hazard analyses.

4.1.4.2 Daily seismic hazard results for Hveragerði

To track the temporal evolution of increased hazard value during the June 2000 seismic sequence, we determine the daily PSHA results for 7 days starting from 18 June 2000 (1 day after the strong earthquake on 17 June with Mw 6.4) until 24 June 2000 (3 days after the 21 June Mw 6.5 event). In all cases, the forecasting time interval is 24 hours.

Figure 19 depicts the forecasted hazard curves for PGA thresholds calculated from individual GMPEs at Hveragerði in south Iceland (TB3). The results are generated for seven forecasting intervals from 18 June 2000 until 24 June 2000. The hazard curves corresponding to the CY14, Z06 and Kea20 branches for a hypocentral depth of 10 km and a maximum magnitude of 7.4 are displayed by solid lines, dashed lines, and dotted lines, respectively. The daily rate of exceedance is displayed on the right panels and the daily probability of exceedance is depicted on the left panels. Red curves show the short-term hazard values and black curves indicate the conventional PSHA results. Note that to assess the short-term hazard curves, the daily forecasted seismicity (i.e. number of forecasted events occurring in a cell within the aftershock zone during the specified time interval) determined from the Bayesian spatiotemporal ETAS model is used. As can be seen in Figure 19, the hazard curves illustrate a significant increase in the daily rate of exceedance compared to the conventional daily hazard curves across all intensity thresholds. This can be observed clearly for all forecasts from 18 June to 24 June. However, the level of increase decreases from 18 to 21 June from day to day. However, the forecasted daily PSHA for 22 June 2000 reaches higher values relative to the previous day. The reason is the occurrence of a strong earthquake with Mw 6.5 on 21 June 2000, which triggered a large number of aftershocks.

Forecasting interval	Daily seismic hazard curves for PGA at Hveragerði (aftershock zone: SISZ+RPOR)	
18 June		
19 June		
20 June		
21 June		

Figure 19. Daily seismic hazard curves for PGA at Hveragerði in south Iceland (TB3) for seven forecasting intervals from 18 June 2000 until 24 June 2000. The aftershock zone defined for ETAS-based seismicity forecasting is the whole south Iceland region including SISZ and RPOR. The hazard curves correspond to a hypocentral depth of 10 km and a maximum magnitude of 7.4. Three dotted, solid, and dashed lines represent results gained employing the three GMPEs of Kowsari et al. (2020), Chiou and Youngs (2014) and Zhao et al. (2006), respectively.

Figure 20 illustrates the final conventional and short-term hazard curves for Hveragerði obtained from the combined logic tree branches. For the 18 June forecasting interval, the daily probability of exceedance of 0.5 g is $4 \cdot 10^{-5}$ from conventional hazard assessment, while for the short-term PSHA, the daily probability of exceeding 0.5 g is forecasted to be $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$. This means that the daily forecasted hazard increased by a factor of 150 with respect to the conventional hazard value.

The forecasted PGA values for a 10% and 2% probability of exceedance in 50 years (i.e. 475 and 2475 years return periods), are 0.65 g and 1.0 g, respectively, one day after 17 June large earthquake. The forecasted PGAs for 24 June 2000 - three days after the 21 June destructive earthquake - are

0.3 g and 0.5 g, respectively. As visible from Figure 19 and Figure 20, PGA estimates with 10% exceedance probability in 50 years obtained from the CY14 and Kea20 models are significantly larger than the one from the Z06 model. This is observed in both short-term and conventional hazard assessment. Such discrepancy highlights the impact of different GMPEs and the importance of using an appropriate set of GMPEs for the region understudy as well as capturing uncertainty within the hazard calculation.

Figure 20. Daily hazard curve obtained from conventional (black curves) and short-term PSHA framework (red curves) for Hveragerði (TB3-south Iceland). The results are presented for two forecasting intervals (18 and 24 June 2000).

Figure 21. Annual probability of exceedance of PGA for Reykjavik and Selfoss towns using conventional and backbone approaches (Figure extracted from Kowsari et al. (2021))

According to the recent long-term PSHA study performed by Kowsari et al. (unpublished), the hazard for the 10% probability of exceedance of PGA in 50 years is approximately 0.6 g for Selfoss (see Figure 21). Note that Selfoss is 12 km from Hveragerði. In scaled backbone approach, a single ground motion model is identified as the backbone model and then scaled to describe a range of median ground motions that captures the epistemic uncertainty. The scaling factors represent the influence of uncertainties in the seismological properties of the ground motion in the target region such as local characteristics of stress-drop and attenuation (see Weatherill et al. (2020) Weatherill and Douglas (2018) for more information). Capturing uncertainty associated with the GMPEs using the backbone approach, this hazard value varies from 0.38 g - 0.85 g (Kowsari et al., unpublished) This highlights the importance of choosing appropriate GMPEs for the purpose of hazard analyses as well as capturing uncertainty in the final estimated measures.

The hazard values obtained here for south Iceland are preliminary and the fundamental inputs into seismic hazard assessment for this testbed are currently under evaluation. Therefore, the results must be taken with caution as they need to be thoroughly validated.

4.1.5 Software description

The software package is described in Deliverable 3.5.

4.1.6 Conclusions

In order to evaluate the feasibility of operational earthquake forecasting for one of the testbed 3 towns in South Iceland by anticipating aftershocks that follow large-magnitude earthquakes within the SISZ as well as determining the evolving seismic hazard at Hveragerði by conducting a short-term seismic hazard assessment, we carried out a comprehensive retrospective forecasting experiment on a recent seismic sequence occurring in the south Iceland seismic zone in June 2000. For this purpose, we apply a Bayesian epidemiological type (ETAS family) spatio-temporal aftershock clustering model, which showed promising results in the case of modelling the 2016 Amatrice seismic sequence in central Italy (Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017). The model exploits the Bayesian inference framework and

Markov Chain Monte Carlo simulations for adaptively learning the ETAS parameters based on data from the ongoing sequence. Based on a revised earthquake catalogue (Panzer et al. 2016), we generate short-term spatial forecasts of seismicity rates along with updated joint probability distributions of ETAS model parameters. The results indicate that forecasting the first mainshock on 17 June 2000 (Mw 6.4) is challenging due to the apparent absence of foreshocks in the few days before. However, the ETAS model is capable of forecasting the increase in seismicity after the first strong shock as well as its spatial distribution including the area in which the second main shock on 21 June 2000 (Mw 6.5) occurred. Overall, this study improves our understanding of the space-time characterization of impending large earthquakes in TB3.

The short-term (24-hrs forecasting time interval) seismicity rates from the Bayesian ETAS model are directly incorporated into the seismic hazard framework. We provide the short-term probability of exceeding the PGA threshold at the TB locality of Hveragerði town in the SISZ and compare the results with the seismic hazard values obtained from a conventional PSHA (i.e. long-term). To capture the epistemic uncertainty in aftershock hazard assessment, the logic tree framework integrates three branching levels of maximum magnitudes, ground motion models, and hypocentral depths. The comparison shows that the short-term hazard values increase by factors ranging from 10 to 1000 by decreasing PGAs during the June 2000 aftershock sequence (i.e. for 24-hrs forecasting intervals from 18 June to 24 June 2000). The relative increase in local hazard values allows the conveyance of scientific information that may facilitate effective mitigation actions to authorities and decision-makers. Mitigation actions initiated by this increased probability mainly focuses the preparedness against earthquakes that may cause new damage or increase progressive damage due to the mainshock.

4.2 Developed models for Patras and Aegio testbed (TB4)

4.2.1 Introduction

The Gulf of Corinth is characterised by some of the highest seismic activity in Europe. This area covers the third-largest city in Greece (Patras) in terms of population, with important infrastructure facilities, including a large port. There are also a variety of geological structures in the region, a fault spanning the city (the Agia Triada Fault) as well as many public buildings, schools and heritage monuments. Additionally, the Rio–Antirrio bridge crosses the Gulf of Corinth near Patras and is one of the world's longest multi-span cable-stayed bridges and longest of the fully suspended type. The town of Aegio is also located in the region. It is famous for the topographic plateau across the main fault (the latest major earthquake was on June 15, 1995). There are also two further towns, Kalavryta and Lidorikion, in the region. In the following, we briefly summarize the available recent literature regarding the seismic hazard in Greece.

Moratto et al. (2007) presented a deterministic seismic hazard analysis for shallow earthquakes in Greece, including estimates of the maximum expected ground motion. Time-independent and time-dependent seismic hazard in Greece was investigated in terms of macroseismic intensity by Papaioannou and Papazachos (2000) for 144 sites consisting of cities, towns, and villages. They concluded that the time-dependent seismic hazard results are in good agreement with the observed seismicity during the period 150 A.D. to 1995 in the study regions.

A detailed area-source seismic zonation model for shallow earthquakes in the broader Aegean area containing 113 zones was proposed by Vamvakaris et al. (2016). This model is based on seismicity as well as available seismotectonic and neotectonic information to represent similar active faulting

characteristics. A detailed investigation of the catalogue completeness, for the recent instrumental period, was also conducted. The seismicity parameters, such as Gutenberg-Richter values for the 113 proposed zones, were calculated, and their spatial distribution is also considered.

Spatio-temporal earthquake clustering in the western Corinth gulf was investigated by Karagianni et al. (2013) by considering geological, seismological, and geodetic aspects. The results revealed complicated tectonic behaviour as well as proof that seismicity is not random in the area and forms distinctive clusters.

Console et al. (2006) applied a variety of forecasting algorithms to the Greek catalogue during two periods: 1966-1980 and 1981-2002. The forecasting capability was statistically assessed by using the log-likelihood method. Their results revealed that the short-term and long-term methods performed much better than the time-invariant models.

Gospodinov et al. (2007) studied forecasting of eight Greek aftershock sequences after 1975. Karakostas et al. (2014) focused on forecasting the 2013 M 5.8 north Aegean seismic sequence. Latoussakis et al. (1991), Latoussakis and Drakatos (1994), and Drakatos and Latoussakis (1996) studied the possibility of forecasting large earthquakes in Greece for different sequences. They used the modified Omori formula and noted its acceptable accuracy. Telesca et al. (2001) analysed the temporal properties of Greek aftershock sequences. For example, they found a significant variability of Omori's p -value between 0.89 and 1.48.

Kourouklas et al. (2020) investigated short-term spatiotemporal clustering of Greek seismicity for the period from 2008 up to 2018. The employed model used maximum-likelihood estimation using a simulated annealing approach. The model performed well except for the 2008 sequence when five $M_w > 6$ earthquakes occurred.

4.2.2 Seismicity in the region

The temporal and spatial characteristics of the ISC⁴ earthquake catalogue for the Patras and Aegio region between 1980 to 2019 are shown in Figure 22 and Figure 23. The selected seismic sequences are listed in Table 6. In the next sections, for the purpose of applying the Reasenber and Jones model, 13 sequences between 1980 and 2007 are used for the model training, and three sequences between 2007 and 2018 are employed to test the model. However, for the ETAS model, all sequences are used separately and finally, six sequences with a sufficient number of events in their aftershock catalogue are chosen to draw the final conclusions.

⁴ International Seismological Centre (2019), On-line Bulletin, <https://doi.org/10.31905/D808B830>

Figure 22. (top): The magnitudes versus time in the earthquake catalogue between 1980 and 2019 in Testbed 4 (Patras and Aegio region in Greece) including the selected sequences of Table 6 which are shown as letters, and (bottom): the daily number of events with magnitudes greater than 3 versus time in the earthquake catalogue between 1980 and 2019 for Testbed 4 (Patras and Aegio region in Greece).

Figure 23. The spatial distribution of the earthquake catalogue between 1980 and 2019 in Testbed 4, (Patras and Aegio region in Greece).

4.2.3 Results of the Reasenber and Jones model

As seen in the flowchart in Figure 24, the non-informative aftershock parameters are used as prior information for the first sequence in Table 6, and the posterior distributions are calculated during the ten days of the aftershock period. As an example, the aftershock forecast for the Mw6.3 earthquake on 25th February 1981 is shown in Figure 25. As seen in Figure 25, the Reasenber and Jones model results are relatively in good agreement with the number of observed events, until eight days after the mainshock, another severe event occurs. This drawback has been reported in the literature as well, e.g. see Kourouklas et al. (2020). Figure 26 shows the Reasenber and Jones model parameters that are updated on a daily basis, using the Bayesian approach. For the next 12 sequences in Table 6, the prior parameters are taken as the mean values of the previous sequence's posterior distribution. The mean and standard deviation for the Reasenber and Jones model corresponding to the 13 training sequences are shown in Figure 27, and the results of the next 12 training sequences are shown in Figure 18 to Figure 41 in Appendix B. This information is proposed as the generic a prior information for the study region and also used as the prior distribution for the three testing sequences in Table 6. The results for the testing sequences are provided in Figure 28 to Figure 33.

Table 6. The seismic sequences, selected for training (13 events) and testing (3 events), respectively, between 1980 and 2019 used to study aftershock parameters.

Sequence Label	Lat.	Lon.	Mainshock Magnitude (Mm)	Mainshock Date (dd/mm/yyyy)
A	38.07	22.91	5.2	25/02/1981
B	37.82	20.07	5.2	29/06/1981
C	38.09	20.28	6.8	17/01/1983
D	38.17	20.46	6.2	23/03/1983
E	38.36	22.11	5.2	02/01/1984
F	38.31	22.10	5.6	11/02/1984
G	37.86	20.92	5.8	16/10/1988
H	38.27	20.39	5.6	23/01/1992
I	37.68	21.50	5.4	26/03/1993
J	38.39	22.28	6.5	15/06/1995
K	37.50	20.80	6.6	18/11/1997
L	38.82	20.58	5.5	14/08/2003
M	37.57	20.95	5.0	17/04/2006
N	37.96	21.45	6.1	08/06/2008
O	38.19	20.51	6.1	26/01/2014
P	37.53	20.62	6.8	25/10/2018

Training sequences

Testing sequences

Figure 24. The Reasenberg and Jones 1989 approach flowchart, adapted for this study.

Figure 25. Aftershock forecasting following the Mw 5.2 event on 25th February 1981, sequence 'A' in Table 6, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during the ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue during the forecast interval.

Figure 26. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in the Reasenberg and Jones model following the Mw 5.2 event on 25th February 1981, sequence 'A' in Table 6, (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 27. Means and corresponding standard deviations of the aftershock parameters based on the 13 selected training seismic sequences in Table 6.

Figure 28. Aftershock forecasting following the Mw 6.1 event on 8th June 2008, sequence ‘N’ in Table 6, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during the ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): the magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue during the forecast interval.

Figure 29. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in the Reasenberg and Jones model following the Mw 6.1 event on 8th June 2008, sequence 'N' in Table 6, (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 30. Aftershock forecasting following the Mw 6.1 event on 26th January 2014, sequence ‘O’ in Table 6, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during the ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): the magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue during the forecast interval.

Figure 31. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in the Reasenberg and Jones model following the M 6.1 event on 26th January 2014, sequence 'O' in Table 6, (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 32. Aftershock forecasting following the Mw 6.8 event on 25th October 2018, sequence ‘P’ in Table 6, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during the ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): the magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue during the forecast interval.

Figure 33. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in the Reasenberg and Jones model following the Mw 6.8 event on 25th October 2018, sequence 'P' in Table 6, (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

4.2.4 Results of the ETAS model

The selected seismic sequences in Table 6 are spatially shown in Figure 23 by letter codes. The aftershock zone is selected between 20-23E and 37.5-39N and meshed on the grid of 0.01×0.01 degrees. The forecast interval is defined as 1 day (24 hours), and the starting time is 0.0 UTC. The magnitude of completeness is calculated using ZMAP throughout the entire study (Wiemer 2001).

The forecasted short-term spatial distribution of seismicity in the region is shown in Figure 34 for a forecast interval of one day (24 hours) starting at 0.00 UTC on 26th October 2018. The results for the remaining sequences are provided in Appendix C in Figures 42 to 56. As can be seen in Figure 34, higher seismicity is forecasted for the closest distances to the mainshock. The total probabilities of exceeding different magnitude thresholds are shown at the left-bottom corner. It is worth noting that this probability depends on the aftershock zone area and cannot be interpreted as a forecast of a specific event at a certain location. In other words, these probabilities are allocated to the whole aftershock region and can be increased by reducing the area of the selected aftershock zone around the mainshock zone.

Figure 34. The spatial distribution of seismicity (rate per km^2) in the aftershock zone for the 26th October 2018 (sequence P in Table 6). The forecast interval is 24 hours, starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$, which is the magnitude of completeness, to $M=7.5$.

One key parameter that is worth emphasising is the number of forecasted events with magnitude greater than or equal to M_c , which is named $N(M > M_c)$ hereafter. The results of $N(M > M_c)$ for the 16 sequences in Table 6 are shown in Figure 35 showing the mean, 2, 16, 84, and 98 percentiles (Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017). As can be seen in Figure 35, the 98 percentiles are in good agreement with the observed number of events with magnitude greater than or equal to M_c . Since it is reasonable to take the most productive sequences in Table 6 into account, the six seismic sequences (C, D, K, N, O, and P) are considered when drawing conclusions for summarizing the prior ETAS information in Table 7.

Figure 35. The number of forecasted events with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness and comparison with the observed data.

As discussed earlier, one concern in the ETAS approach is how to select a reasonable prior θ . The posterior distributions of θ for the six seismic sequences (C, D, K, N, O, and P) are shown in Table 7, which reports the eight parameters of ETAS (along with their dispersions). Only the first five parameters are updated by the MCMC algorithm during each sequence. Furthermore, the average value for each parameter is shown in the last row of Table 7, which we propose to be employed as a reasonable set of prior θ for further implementation.

Table 7. The posterior distributions of ETAS parameters for six sequences of Table 6 ($\beta = b \times \ln(10)$).

Sequence	β	σ_β	c	σ_c	d	σ_d	p	σ_p	q	σ_q	K	σ_K	Kr	σ_{Kr}	Kt	σ_{Kt}
C	0.858	0.482	0.037	0.014	1.636	0.402	0.862	0.587	2.366	1.096	0.712	0.303	0.115	0.129	0.069	0.037
D	1.991	0.005	0.057	0.007	1.018	0.01	2.322	0.158	1.289	0.018	2.967	1.232	0.15	0.016	0.017	0.009
K	0.828	0.845	0.032	0.019	4.678	2.946	1.167	0.607	1.454	0.297	0.608	0.399	0.119	0.092	0	0
N	1.71	0.005	0.045	0.006	1.014	0.009	2.629	0.186	1.293	0.028	6.87	3.637	0.163	0.025	0.013	0.008
O	1.703	0.176	0.018	0.008	1.05	0.039	1.134	0.222	1.239	0.043	1.17	0.736	0.081	0.02	0.037	0.024
P	1.622	0.121	0.044	0.009	1.038	0	1.624	0.244	1.172	0.031	2.383	0.457	0.065	0.015	0.033	0
Average Over	1.452	0.272	0.039	0.01	1.739	0.568	1.623	0.334	1.469	0.252	2.451	1.127	0.116	0.049	0.028	0.013

4.2.4.1 The sensitivity of the results to the grid size

The ETAS results are monitored versus the refinement in the grid size in the aftershock zone. For this purpose, five grid spacing sizes are investigated, i.e. 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2 degrees. The number of forecasted events with magnitude greater than or equal to M_c as well as the total probability of exceeding different magnitude thresholds in the aftershock zone are shown in Table 8. Reasonable grid size can be chosen based on these results using the criterion that the difference between the results of different grid sizes converges. As seen in Table 8, a reasonable grid size is between 0.01 and 0.02 degrees. Considering that the 98 percentile forecast scored best when comparing observed and modelled numbers of events, a grid size of 0.01 degree is chosen for this study.

Table 8. The ETAS results for sequence P of Table 6 (26th October 2018) for different grid sizes.

Grid size (degree)	Number of forecasted events, $M > M_c$ (No. of observed is 53)			Total probability in the aftershock zone				
	mean	84 percentile	98 percentile	$P(M > 3.6)$	$P(M > 4.5)$	$P(M > 5.5)$	$P(M > 6.5)$	$P(M > 7.5)$
0.2	13	19	31	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.1
0.1	21	30	48	1	1	0.7	0.2	0.1
0.05	31	40	51	1	1	0.8	0.3	0.1
0.02	26	35	47	1	1	0.7	0.3	0.1
0.01	26	37	56	1	1	0.7	0.3	0.1

4.2.5 Results of the short-term seismic hazard analysis model

The aftershock zone in Testbed 4 is subdivided into 11 area sources as defined in ESHM13 and shown in Figure 36. The results of the conventional PSHA and their comparison with the results of ESHM13 are shown in Figure 37. The top-left graph in Figure 37 is for the annual probability of exceedance, and the top-right graph is for the annual rate of exceedance. A Poisson distribution is assumed between the annual rate and the annual probability of exceedance. The difference between our results and ESHM13 are resulting from differences in source definitions (e.g. area source, SEIFA source and FSBG model) and logic-trees. It is worth mentioning that a sophisticated logic-tree is not appropriate for the purpose of Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF), since the computational effort should be kept to a minimum level in order to obtain the results at a reasonable time after a mainshock.

Figure 36. 11 area sources in the aftershock zone based on ESHM13.

In the next step, $\lambda(M > M_{min})$ is altered to account for the summation of background seismicity (from conventional PSHA) and the short-term seismicity from the ETAS results. The hazard integral (Eq. 6) is computed again based on this increased seismicity. The results of this time-dependent PSHA are shown in the bottom-left (daily probability of exceedance) and bottom-right (daily rate of exceedance) panels in Figure 37. The results for the remaining sequences are provided in Appendix D in Figures 57 to 71. It is worth mentioning that the conventional hazard curve represents a lower bound for this short-term hazard curve, since we assume that the short-term seismicity can only result in increasing the conventional hazard.

Figure 37. Short-term PSHA, (top-left): the conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 results, (top-right): the conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): the short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

The ratio of the short-term hazard curve to the conventional hazard curve is defined as the probability gain (PG), which is a function of PGA. As can be seen in Figure 37, the PG parameter decreases as PGA increases. The maximum PG parameter, over the entire range of PGA, is shown in Figure 38 for all sixteen sequences. As visible in Figure 38, the highest PG is around 55 in the case of sequence N. This PG is a useful input to the OEF cost-benefit analysis described in Deliverable 3.1 of the TURNkey project.

Figure 38. Probability gain (the ratio of short-term hazard to conventional time-independent hazard) over the range of considered PGAs, for different seismic sequences described in Table 6.

4.2.5.1 Effects of non-seismic input data

Non-seismic measurements (radon) can indicate an imminent increase in the seismicity rate within the study region. Hence, based on the results of the study in Chapter 4.3, we consider two cases. The first non-seismic case (non-seismic no.1) corresponds to an increase of 17 and 66% in the seismicity rate, respectively, in terms of mean and mean plus one standard deviation. The second non-seismic case (non-seismic no.2) corresponds to an increase of 101 and 201% in the seismicity rate, respectively, in terms of mean and mean plus one standard deviation. The non-seismic data is combined with the conventional short-term PSHA in a logic-tree framework, as shown in Figure 39. The weights are assigned based on expert judgement. Additionally, an extreme case is also considered assigning a weight of 100% to the non-seismic branch no.2.

The results of the short-term hazard with and without non-seismic data are shown in Figure 40, which confirms that the non-seismic information only has a minor influence on the final hazard curve, at least with the assumed values for the radon gas emission increasing the seismicity rate. The two non-seismic cases increased the maximum PG, over the entire range of PGA from 21 to around 22 and 25, respectively. However, it increases to 36 when only 100% of non-seismic no.2 is taken into consideration within the logic-tree framework. Apparently, this effect will be larger if stronger correlations between seismicity and non-seismic parameters are found.

Figure 39. The implemented logic-tree within the short-term time-dependent PSHA.

Figure 40. Short-term PSHA by consideration of non-seismic data, (left): the short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve. The non-seismic case no. 1 represents the average increase in seismicity due to the radon measurement, equal to 17% and the average plus one sigma equal to 66%. The non-seismic case no. 2 represents the average increase in seismicity due to the radon measurement, equal to 101% and the average plus one sigma equal to 201%. A case of using 100% contribution of non-seismic no. 2 is also included.

4.2.6 Software description

The software package is described in Deliverable 3.5.

4.2.7 Conclusions

Three models are adapted to the Patras and Aegio region of Greece, which represents Testbed 4. The first model is the Reasenberg and Jones (1989) model to forecast the number of events with magnitude greater than or equal to a threshold following a mainshock. This model is applied to sixteen selected seismic sequences. The results are relatively in good agreement with the observed data; however, this model is not able to capture the spatial distributions of events. Therefore, as the second model, a very recent and advanced ETAS model is applied that is based on the spatial distribution of events and utilises a Bayesian and MCMC framework in order to forecast the seismicity in the region by adapting to the recently registered observations. The results reveal that there is a good agreement between the number of forecasted events with the number of observed earthquakes, especially if the mean plus one standard deviation is taken into consideration. The third employed model is a coupled model, which incorporates the ETAS seismicity into a short-term PSHA model. The output consists of daily seismic hazard curves, which can further be used for vulnerability and loss assessment. The influence of non-seismic parameters, e.g. radon, in this case, on the short-term daily hazard curve, is also investigated.

4.3 Developed models for Romania

4.3.1 Model description

4.3.1.1 Multidisciplinary monitoring network in the Vrancea area

We represent the monitoring network in Figure 41. The most important information is the distance of stations from epicentral areas. Vrancea generates important intermediate-depth earthquakes in-between two regions: Nereju and Gura Teghii. Panciu (PANC) is a reference station, because is located outside of seismic area.

Figure 41. Multidisciplinary monitoring network in the Vrancea area, Romania seismicity

The curvature of the Carpathian Mountains is characterized by many faults and intermediate earthquakes. The positions of the monitoring stations are marked in red (Figure 41 and Figure 42). The role of monitoring stations is to highlight the phenomena that precede intensive seismic periods for a short-term forecast. The monitoring equipment is chosen according to the geological features of the location. For example, radon detectors have been moved several times in search of a correlation of radon emissions with seismic activity. Every station sends information to NIEP centre (National Institute for Earth Physics from Romania) automatically, where a server saves and displays the data, and computes a power spectrum analysis in real-time.

Radon monitoring is indoor in the air near the ground. The used sensors are Radon Scout PLUS, (https://sarad.de/product-detail.php?lang=en_US&cat_ID=2&p_ID=37), produced by SARAD. Processing is performed manually with the manufacturer's software. Usually, data is downloaded weekly. The storage capacity of the equipment covers over 1 year of data at a sampling rate of 3 hours (minimum can be 1 hour). Table 9 compiles a summary of the monitoring stations involved in this research.

Figure 42. Monitoring area, main faults, seismic stations (map by Raileanu et al., 2005, 2006)

Table 9. Summary of radon monitoring stations

Station Code	Location	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m)	Sensors position	Measurement
BISRd	Bisoca	45.5481	26.7099	823	Indoor in a brick building.	Radon, infrasound, ULF, seismic
LOPRd	Lopatari	45.4738	26.5686	645	Indoor in a metallic case	Radon, CO ₂ +CO
NEHRd	Nehoiu	45.4272	26.2952	513	Indoor in a metallic case	CO ₂ , radon, ions, seismic
VRId	Vrancioaia	45.8657	26.7277	424	Indoor in a brick building. This station was installed on 21 August 2017 and retired on 21 July 2020	Acoustic, telluric currents, radon, ions
PLRd2	Plostina	45.8513	26.6497	617	Inside a 0.5 m cavity	Radon, infrasound

Data Structure

Tectonic stress produces a degassing process that generates CO₂ and radon. The radon stations generate a text files which is appended to the history of radon recorded at this station with a software designed for this purpose. The result is a list of files per day with a sample rate of 1 minute. The data structure is presented in Figure 43. The file BISRd_181004_200909.txt is a text file with Tab delimiter and represents the radon in Bisoca from 4 October 2018 to 9 September 2020 (Figure 44). The ‘Analysis’ folder contains the data per month (format yymm, 1801 means January 2018) with files per day. An example is in Figure 45 where we used EXCEL to read the file BISRd200903_00.xls. According to the format, the file contains the recorded data on 3 September 2020. This information is accessible by FTP from the TURNkey platform.

Figure 43. Data structure accessible via FTP

```

BISRd_181004_200909.txt - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
Comment:
BISRd_200909
Data exported from "RSC1031_10_4_2018 8-41 ... 9_9_2020 8-41.rvx"
Radon-Scout PLUS
Serial Number: 1031
Start Test: 18/10/04 05:41
End Test: 20/09/09 08:41
Sample Time: 16947.0 hours
Data Records: 5649

RESULTS

Radon Average: 69 Bq/m³
Error: 0.3 %
Radon Exposure: 1167011 Bqh/m³

Time Radon Error Temp. rel. Hum. Pres. Tilt ROI1
      Bq/m³ % °C % mbar cts
18/10/04 08:41 80 21 16.5 47 927 0 23
18/10/04 11:41 160 15 17.5 47 928 0 46
.....
20/09/08 23:41 132 16 24.5 46 930 0 38
20/09/09 02:41 139 16 24.0 46 929 0 40
20/09/09 05:41 111 18 23.5 45 929 0 32
20/09/09 08:41 62 24 22.5 46 930 0 18
    
```

Figure 44. Radon text file

Finally, Figure 46 shows the radon measurements recorded in the different stations previously mentioned in Table 9. As we can see, the radon measurements recorded at LOPRd and NEHRd has a very low amplitude, with numerous spikes. PLRd2 shows a recording which is incomplete for many days. Only the stations BISRd and VRId show a recording which is complete and has a considerable amplitude. Besides, both stations are installed inside a place made with brick walls.

BISRd_200903_00.xls - Excel

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Radon	Error	Temp	rel Hum	Pres	Time Date
2	ON	ON	ON	ON	ON	
3	108	18	27.5	43	922	20/09/03 00:00:00
4	108	18	27.5	43	922	20/09/03 00:01:00
5	108	18	27.5	43	922	20/09/03 00:02:00
6	108	18	27.5	43	922	20/09/03 00:03:00
7	108	18	27.5	43	922	20/09/03 00:04:00
8	108	18	27.5	43	922	20/09/03 00:05:00
9	108	18	27.5	43	922	20/09/03 00:06:00
10	108	18	27.5	43	922	20/09/03 00:07:00

Figure 45. Example of radon file converted in a general format. Radon units are Bq/m³, Temperature is in Celsius degrees, relative humidity (in %) and pressure in mbar. The sample rate is 1 minute.

Figure 46. Radon measurements in the different stations (see Figure 41).

4.3.1.2 *Seismicity in the Vrancea region.*

The Vrancea zone represents the most active seismic zone in Europe and is located on the Eastern edge of the strongly bent Carpathian arc. In this area, shallow seismicity with moderate earthquakes ($M_w < 5.6$) is found together with intermediate-depth activity featuring strong earthquakes. A detailed description can be found in Deliverable 3.1.

According to Figure 46, we select a seismic catalogue covering the whole period in which there are radon recordings. To assure a correct computation of the GR parameter for the first days of the radon measurement, the seismic catalogue starts several months before the starting day of the radon measurements. Hence, the seismicity from 01 July 2015 to 30 August 2020 (Figure 47) is used to seek correlations between the activity rate (λ_m) of earthquakes with magnitudes greater than a threshold magnitude M and the radon activity. The catalogue is part of the official INFP catalogue that can be found in text format here: <http://www.infp.ro/index.php?i=romplus> and it contains 2158 events with moment magnitude range (ΔM_w) between 1.2 and 5.5 and depth from 1.0 to 196 km. As we can see, nearly all the intermediate and deep events take place within the SHARE seismic zone named Vrancea. BISRd station has been chosen as the monitoring site so the earthquakes have been selected by isolating those events that could generate soil radon anomalies at the monitoring site. As we can see the earthquakes are found mainly at a distance between 10 to 45 km. Subsequently, according to Papachristodoulou et al. (2020), the radon station records all the anomalies due to earthquakes with magnitude $M \geq 4.0$ and most of the anomalies due to earthquakes with magnitude $M_w \geq 3.0$. Hence, the magnitude of completeness for the radon anomalies should be between 3.0 and 4.0.

Figure 48a shows the distribution of events by year (binned by month), the magnitude distribution, and the depth distribution. There is a mean of 30 events by month approximately. Most of the earthquakes have magnitudes greater than 2.5. Most of the events have a depth greater than 50 km, i.e., 39% are shallow seismicity (1 to 50 km), 22% are intermediate seismicity (51 to 105 km) and 39% deep seismicity (> 106 km). The GR parameters of the full catalogue (Figure 47 and Table 10), shows that the b-value is 1.12. The processing is performed using ZMAP software (Wiemer 2001; Wiemer and Wyss 2002) employing maximum likelihood estimation (MLE). The magnitude of completeness (2.9) is obtained using the maximum curvature method (MCE). Table 10 shows a summary of the results and compares these values with the obtained if the events are classified by depth range. As we can see, the shallow seismicity only includes earthquake with magnitude ≤ 3.0 .

Therefore, the full catalogue is used to investigate the correlations between the activity rate and radon emissions because we assure enough number of events to estimate the temporal evolution of the b-value and the activity rate.

4.3.1.3 *Temporal evolution of the GR parameters in the region*

A continuous GR parameter time series is computed from the Vrancea full catalogue using the methodology explained in Section 3.4.4.1. The computation has been done fitting the a-value and the b-value (Figure 49). Although our approach is not trying to use the radon signal as a precursor, it is interesting to observe that the three $M > 5.0$ events are preceded by a decrease of the b-value.

Figure 47. Top: Seismic catalogue from July 2015 to August 2020. The SHARE intermediate-deep seismic zones and the location of the Radon Stations have also been represented. Bottom: Gutenberg-Richter law regression.

Table 10. Summary of the results

Catalogue	(daily) a	b	Mc	Daily Rate (>4.0)	Events	ΔM_w
Full	2.8875	1.12	2.9	0.0256	2158	1.2 -5.5
Shallow	2.2895	1.28	1.7	0.0015	835	1.2 – 3.0
Intermediate	2.6885	1.39	2.7	0.0013	488	1.2 – 5.5
Deep	2.5455	1.05	2.9	0.0221	835	2.2 – 5.5
Intermediate-Deep	2.8815	1.12	2.9	0.0252	1323	1.2 -5.5

Figure 48. Seismicity distribution of the full catalogue

Figure 49. Temporal evolution of the GR parameters and temporal distribution of the seismicity. Orange discontinuous lines in a and b parameter represent the uncertainty of the estimation. The bottom figure represents the temporal distribution of the seismicity with the three observed Mw 5.5 earthquakes.

4.3.1.4 Correlation between seismicity and radon time series

In this section, the methodology developed to find the potential correlation between the recorded seismicity in terms of daily seismic activity rate (section 4.3.1.3) and the radon concentration time series is described at the example of the BISRd station (section 4.3.1.1).

In Figure 50, the radon time series recorded from 01 January 2016 to 30 August 2020 is shown (top) and compared with the temporal distribution of the seismicity (bottom). The radon signal exhibits periodic oscillations, which are also observed in meteorological time series (e.g. temperature) (Figure 51). Therefore, non-seismic effects as barometric pressure, temperature, wind, and rainfall can influence radon concentration recordings. Subsequently, the effect of these non-seismic parameters have to be reduced in order to uncover anomalies in radon emissions before attempting to associate those anomalies with seismic activity (Piersanti et al. 2016; Papachristodoulou et al. 2020).

Figure 50. a) Radon time series registered at the BISRd station from 01 January 2016 to 30 August 2020, b) temporal distribution of the seismicity (starting 01 July 2015).

To remove the annual oscillations, the signal is fitted by a sine wave. In our case, the sine function is defined as:

$$y = A \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} x + \varphi\right) + D$$

The coefficients to be fitted are amplitude (A), phase delay (φ) and offset (D). The period (T) will be fixed to 365 days as proposed by Kobayashi et al. (2015).

For the analysed radon time series, the best fitting provides the following results:

coefficients (with 95% confidence bounds):

$$\begin{aligned} A &= 35.65 (32.56, 38.74) \\ \varphi &= -0.1886 (-0.2748, -0.1024) \\ D &= 63.52 (61.33, 65.7) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 51. Radon, pressure, temperature and relative humidity time series registered at the BISRD station from 01 January 2016 to 30 August 2020

In Figure 52, the sine wave representing the best fit to the radon time series is shown as well as the radon signal from which annual oscillations have been removed.

a)

b)

Figure 52. a) Radon time series (blue line) and the best fitting sine wave (red line). b) Radon times series without the annual oscillations.

In the next step, any potential linear trend is estimated and removed from the signal. In this case, the best fit provides the following results:

$$y = p1*x + p2$$

coefficients (with 95% confidence bounds):

$$p1 = 0.0301 (0.02576, 0.03445)$$

$$p2 = -7.4e+04 (-8.468e+04, -6.333e+04)$$

a)

b)

In

Figure 53. the estimated linear trend and the cleaned signal are also shown.

a)

b)

Figure 53. a) Radon time series (blue line) and the best linear fit (red line). b) Radon times series without the linear trend.

Finally, in the last step of the pre-processing, a moving averaged filter is applied in order to smooth the signal. In practice, the filter averages over 80 days. In Figure 54, the time series together with the smoothed signal are shown for the radon (Figure 54a) and the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with a threshold magnitude $M > 4.0$ (Figure 54b)

a)

b)

Figure 54. Time series (blue) and the signal after the 80 days moving averaged filter (red): (a) Radon, (b) logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate $\lambda_m > 4.0$.

Once the signals have been pre-processed and smoothed, the correlation analysis is carried out in order to find the mathematical relation between both signals.

Initially, we find the best correlation for 100-days windows of radon emissions and the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate, applying a ± 40 day lag (Figure 55). The analysis is repeated for each day of the time series. Different values of window length and time lags were tested, but no significant differences in the final results are observed.

Figure 55. Example of correlation analysis: time window length equals 100 days, and lag time is ± 40 days.

For the best daily correlation coefficient, the associated lag is obtained. Then, once the best correlation coefficient and time lag for each day of the time series are obtained, the best linear regression between the smoothed radon anomalies (Figure 54a) and the smoothed logarithm of the

daily seismic activity rate (Figure 54b) windows is computed for all windows with a correlation coefficient higher than 0.9 (Figure 56).

Figure 56. The correlation coefficient for each day of analysis

Finally, the mean and the standard deviation of the linear fit are estimated, and a correlation-based process is applied in both signals in order to analyse any possible time delay. In practice, in the current example, the relation between the radon anomaly time series and the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with a threshold magnitude $M > 4.0$ series is expressed as:

$$\log (\lambda_m > 4.0) = \mathbf{aa} \cdot (\text{radon anom.}) + \mathbf{bb}$$

$$\mathbf{aa} = 0.0101 \pm 0.0062$$

$$\mathbf{bb} = -1.3038 \pm 0.1635$$

Time delay: 0 days

Applying this relation to the smoothed radon time series, the smoothed logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with magnitude $M > 4.0$ signal can be predicted and compared with the smoothed logarithm of the observed one. This comparison is shown in Figure 57.

Figure 57. Smoothed logarithm of the smoothed observed daily seismic activity rate (blue) and the predicted rates and uncertainties (red) obtained from the radon signal

Finally, the process is repeated using the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with magnitude thresholds from $M=3.0$ to $M=6.0$ in steps of 0.1 (Figure 58). Hence, different aa and bb parameters are found for each one of the threshold magnitudes. Then, linear regressions between aa , bb and the magnitude are carried out to obtain the coefficients $f_1(M)$ and $f_2(M)$ (see the model proposed in Section 3.4.4.1).

Figure 58. Logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate (λ_m) for different threshold magnitudes.

The results for $f_1(M)$ are (Figure 59):

$$f_1(M) = 0.01044 \cdot M - 0.03159 \text{ with corresponding standard deviation}$$

$$\sigma\{f_1(M)\} = 0.006782 \cdot M - 0.02091$$

Figure 59. Correlation between aa and threshold magnitude (left) and corresponding standard deviation σ (right)

The results for $f_2(M)$ are (Figure 60):

$$f_2(M) = -0.7144 \cdot M + 1.557 \text{ with corresponding standard deviation}$$

$$\sigma\{f_2(M)\} = 0.176 \cdot M - 0.5396$$

Figure 60. Correlation between bb and threshold magnitude (left) and corresponding standard deviation σ (right)

Therefore, the initial proposed model is:

$$\log(\lambda_{M>M}) = f_1(M) \text{ (Rn anomaly)} + f_2(M)$$

with

$$f_1(M) = 0.01044 \cdot M - 0.03159$$

$$f_2 (M) = - 0.7144 * M + 1.557$$

From this procedure, we can conclude that it is possible to find a reasonable correlation between the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with a given threshold magnitude and the radon anomalies time series. Besides, from Figure 59 and Figure 60 we can see that the magnitude of completeness for the radon anomalies are approximately 3.8 which is coherent with the influence area chosen for the radon station. However, during the correlation process, we have used the full radon database and we have directly chosen a smoothing parameter of 80 days. The next section carries out a sensitivity study using training and validation data to fix the best smoothing parameter and, therefore, to establish the final proposed model between both variables.

4.3.1.5 Sensitivity analysis of the correlation between seismicity and radon time series.

In the previous section, we have described the proposed methodology by using the complete database of the radon and activity rate time series. Some of the steps as removing the seasonality and linear trend are easily justified. However, the selection of the used smoothing parameter (80 days) to apply both to the radon and seismic time series needs to be calibrated before proposing the final model.

Therefore, we have split the signal into two different sets. The first one is named training set and it is used to fit the model between the radon time series and the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate. The second one is named validation and it is used to check the goodness of the fitness and to support the decision on which is the best model between the two variables.

The training set comprises the first 1325 days of the original sequence, from 1 January 2016 to 18 August 2019. The validation set comprises from 19 August 2019 to 30 September 2020 (409 days). We have preferred using a 75% of the data for the training set to keep enough number of points for obtaining the correlation. Anyway, the validation database covers the occurrence of events in all the range of magnitudes.

The methodology proposed in section 4.3.1.4 was applied to the training set and different lengths of the moving average filter were tested. Figure 83 shows the comparison between the observed logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with a magnitude threshold $M > 4.0$, the smoothed values after applying the corresponding moving average filter, and the predicted logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate after fitting the smoothed seismic signal with the smoothed radon signal.

As we can see, the moving average filter mainly removes the spikes within the observed daily seismic activity rate. The correlation between the predicted and the smoothed rate increase as the smoothing parameter increases. However, the increase of the smoothing parameters decreases the amplitude of the oscillations, which may also provoke an underestimation of the predicted activity rate when compared with the observed time series. In Appendix E, the figures for logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with magnitude thresholds $M > 4.5$ and $M > 5.0$ are found (Appendix E, Figure 72 and Figure 73).

These results have been quantified in terms of mean error of estimation, mean residual and correlation coefficient by comparing the smoothed and predicted rate (Table 11). As it is visible for the three fitted activity rates ($M > 4.0$, $M > 4.5$, and $M > 5.0$), the highest correlation coefficients, lowest mean residual and lowest mean errors of estimation are found when the smoothing parameter for the moving average filter is 30 or 45 days.

Figure 61. Logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with a threshold magnitude $M > 4.0$ using different window lengths for the moving average filter. Training time series.

Therefore, the validation data is used to choose between one of these two values and provide the final prediction model between the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with a magnitude threshold M and the radon anomaly. Table 12 summarizes the results in terms of mean error of estimation, mean residual and correlation coefficients between the observed and the predicted rate. The results confirm the 30-day windows as the best-suited. Figure 62 shows the results obtained for the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with a threshold magnitude $M > 4.0$ and a moving average filter of 30 days applied to the validation data.

Thus, the model for obtaining the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate (λ_M) with a threshold magnitude M using the radon emission data is:

$$\log (\lambda_M) = f_1 (M) (\text{Rn anomaly}) + f_2 (M)$$

with

$$f_1 (M) = 0.0079 \cdot M - 0.0228 \text{ and corresponding standard deviation}$$

$$\sigma\{f_1 (M)\} = 0.0052 \cdot M - 0.0152$$

$$f_2 (M) = -0.7221 \cdot M + 1.6138 \text{ and corresponding standard deviation}$$

$$\sigma\{f_2 (M)\} = 0.1306 \cdot M - 0.3697$$

Table 11. Errors, residuals and correlation coefficients obtained between the predicted and smoothed training time series. Magnitudes threshold of 4.0, 4.5, and 5.0 as well as and different window length of the moving average filter are tested.

15-days window	Magnitude	4.0	4.5	5.0
	Mean Error	0.26	0.37	0.49
	Mean Residual	0.13	0.17	0.21
	Correlation coef.	0.14	0.15	0.14
30-days window	Magnitude	4.0	4.5	5.0
	Error	0.22	0.33	0.45
	Residual	-0.03	0.01	0.04
	Correlation coef.	0.18	0.17	0.17
45-days window	Magnitude	4.0	4.5	5.0
	Error	0.22	0.34	0.47
	Residual	0.07	0.12	0.17
	Correlation coef.	0.18	0.18	0.17
60-days window	Magnitude	4.0	4.5	5.0
	Error	0.22	0.33	0.45
	Residual	0.07	0.11	0.15
	Correlation coef.	0.16	0.16	0.16
80-days window	Magnitude	4.0	4.5	5.0
	Error	0.20	0.31	0.42
	Residual	0.04	0.07	0.08
	Correlation coef.	0.12	0.12	0.11

Table 12. Errors, residuals, and correlation coefficients obtained between the predicted and smoothed validation time series. Magnitudes threshold of 4.0, 4.5, and 5.0, and different window lengths of the moving average filter are tested.

30-days window	Magnitude	4.0	4.5	5.0
----------------	-----------	-----	-----	-----

	Error	0.28	0.42	0.56
	Residual	-0.02	0.03	0.07
	Correlation coef.	0.23	0.20	0.18
45-days window	Magnitude	4.0	4.5	5.0
	Error	0.27	0.42	0.56
	Residual	0.08	0.14	0.20
	Correlation coef.	0.19	0.15	0.13

4.3.2 Real-time operation mode

In the real-time operation, the developed algorithm receives a daily file with the radon measurements recorded by the selected station. The algorithm appends this information to a buffer, which stores data for two years previous to the analysed day. The reason is that the annual oscillations and the linear trend have to be estimated and removed from the signal. Besides, a 30-day moving average filter is subsequently applied to the resulting signal for smoothing. Finally, the algorithm provides a forecast of the predicted increase of the daily seismic activity rate for a given threshold magnitude M above its mean rate within the area under study. In Figure 63, the general flowchart of the proposed algorithm is shown.

Figure 64 shows an example of an application for the whole period also with an initial buffer covering all the previous radon measurements, that is, from 01 January 2016 to 29 September 2020. Assuming that the results are going to be used for a TPSHA with a threshold magnitude of 4.5, then the algorithm is computing the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate for that threshold magnitude, providing a daily value of the percentage of increase (Figure 65) over the background seismicity (mean activity rate).

As we discussed in Section 3.4.4.1 the activity rate obtained from radon measurements can be used within a logic tree in order to compute time dependent seismic hazard results. The chosen values used in Section 4.2.5.1 were taken assuming a behaviour of the radon measurements similar to the days before the 28 October 2019 Vrancea earthquake with a $M_w = 5.5$ (Figure 65). One month before the earthquake, the mean percentage of increase of the daily background activity rate is 17% and five days before the earthquake reaches a 101%.

Figure 62. Logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate for $M > 4.0$, 4.5 and 5.0 using a 30-day moving average filter. Validation time series.

Figure 63 Main flowchart of the developed algorithm

Figure 64 Computation of the predicted mean value of the logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with a threshold magnitude $M > 4.5$ and uncertainties (standard deviation).

Figure 65. Example of the estimated percentage of increase of daily background seismic activity rate with a threshold magnitude $M > 4.5$, and comparison with the occurrence date of earthquakes with magnitude $M > 4.5$ (the y value for the earthquakes was chosen 400 for Mw 5.5 and 300 for Mw 4.6-4.8 for graphical purposes).

4.3.3 Software description

The software package is described in deliverable 3.5.

4.3.4 Conclusions

In the OEF context, a new methodology has been developed for estimating the daily seismic activity rate with a given threshold magnitude from radon measurements. In the first part of the study, known radon and seismic activity rate time series were used in order to study a potential correlation between both signals. It was demonstrated that signal pre-processing is required. Thus, it is crucial to remove both the annual oscillations and a linear trend from the radon time series. Besides, a moving average filter is important for smoothing the signals and removing spikes. After that, a correlation analysis allowed determining the best fit between the radon and the activity rate time series as a function of the magnitude. In this way, the seismic activity rate for any magnitude threshold between $M=3$ and $M=6$ can be estimated directly from the radon time series, just using the parameters of the obtained adjustment. Comparing the obtained results with the mean activity rate on the area under study, the estimated percentage of increase in the daily seismic activity rate is also provided. Finally, it is important to point out that the proposed model cannot be used as a forecast algorithm of an impending earthquake but as a novelty method of computing the daily seismic activity rate using radon measurements.

5 TIME-DEPENDENT LOSS FOR OEF

5.1 Time-dependent loss for Iceland

5.1.1 Data

In April 2020, the most recent exposure database was provided for both towns within TB3 by the national registry of Iceland. The original database is in Icelandic. The unit-by-unit exposure data for TB3 towns are classified as indicated in the following sections. The TB3 exposure data has been provided by the University of Iceland team (Darzi A., Bessason B., Halldorsson B.) in different formats and levels of details to make the use of the testbed 3 exposure database convenient for all partners who are interested in working with the database. The following is a list of data files created in the TURNkey project:

- unit-by-unit data has been provided in Excel and point-shapefile (GIS)
- building-by-building data has been provided in Excel and point-shapefile (GIS) as well as polygon-shapefile (GIS)
- MATLAB structure (*.mat) for buildings including all units' information

A classification based on GEM taxonomy was provided for all the abovementioned databases. Deliverable 4.1 describes the information in detail.

The city of Hveragerði has been chosen to compute a time dependent loss analysis providing effective results for OEF. The residential buildings in the city are classified as 45 masonry buildings (54 dwelling and 8101 m² built area), 595 concrete buildings (725 dwelling and 96370 m² built area), 345 timber buildings (388 dwellings and 52404 m² built area) 86 building with unknown typology (6 dwelling and 876 m² built area). Additionally, Statistic Iceland (<https://statice.is>) reports 2699 inhabitants so we have assumed that the inhabitants in each typology are proportional to the number of dwellings. Hence, there are 124 inhabitants in masonry buildings, 1668 inhabitants in reinforced concrete buildings, 891 inhabitants in timber buildings, and 16 inhabitants in unknown typologies buildings.

5.1.2 Fragility models selected for Hveragerði

For the town Hveragerði in South Iceland, the fragility models for residential buildings and service buildings are based on statistical vulnerability models presented by (Bessason et al. 2020). The common methodology in the literature is to first construct fragility curves and then use them to create and build loss estimation models also called vulnerability models. The fragility models here, for the Icelandic testbeds, are however determined in reversed order, i.e. from the vulnerability models. Due to this reversed order, the methodology for both the loss estimation models and the fragility models is described in the next subsection.

5.1.2.1 Loss estimation models selected for Hveragerði

The loss estimation models for Hveragerði were evaluated from detailed empirical loss data recorded after the two Mw6.5 South Iceland Earthquakes of June 2000. The loss data from these events are complete in the sense they cover all buildings in the affected area where the estimated PGA was greater than 0.05 g, totalling almost 5000 buildings. Originally, a beta regression model was fitted to the data (Ioannou et al. 2018) but due to the high proportion of no-loss buildings in the loss database (~84%) the model was improved by Bessason et al. (2020) by utilizing a zero-inflated beta regression

model (Ospina and Ferrari 2012). The stochastic variable describing the losses is the damage factor, DF , defined as:

$$DF = \frac{\text{Estimated loss}}{\text{Replacement value}}$$

The factor is bounded to be in the range $[0,1]$, where 0 means no-loss, and 1 (100%) means total-loss. The model was fitted to the three main building typologies in the affected region, i.e. low-rise structural wall RC (54% of the residential building stock), timber buildings (36%), and masonry buildings. (9.3%). Only, 0.3% of the building stock does not belong to any of these three classes. Seismic codes were first implemented in Iceland in 1976 and consequently, concrete buildings constructed before that had a limited amount of reinforcement, typically only around openings in structural walls (low code). Most of the buildings are in-situ cast and only a few are using prefabricated elements. Prescribed wind loads in Iceland are among the highest in Europe. The fundamental base value of wind velocity is $v_{b,0}=36$ m/s (CEN, 2002; Icelandic Standards 2010). Consequently, to withstand high wind loads, the Icelandic timber houses are strongly built and well suited to withstand earthquake forces as well. The bottom floor slab and the foundations are usually made of reinforced concrete, as in the concrete houses. The masonry buildings were built of unreinforced manufactured hollow pumice (*high porosity volcanic rock*) blocks in walls and tied together with rigid RC floors. The weighted density of the pumice blocks is low, typically around 14 kN/m³, and consequently the inertia forces are lower than in ordinary Southern Europe stone or clay brick masonry buildings. Masonry buildings were mainly built before 1980 and are no longer constructed. An important characteristic of the Icelandic building stock is how young it is in an international context. No building was constructed before 1870 and 92% of them were constructed after 1940.

The details of the statistical vulnerability models are given in Bessason et al. (2020). The model is constructed by combining a logistical regression model and a conditional beta regression model. Five parameters are used to model each building typology, i.e. two parameters β_0 and β_1 , for the logistical model and three parameters, θ_0 , θ_1 and θ'_0 for the conditional beta model. These parameters are given in Table 13 for the tree main building typologies in Testbed 3. Based on the model parameters in Table 13 the loss estimation curve (vulnerability curve) for each building typology is shown in Figure 66.

Table 13. Estimated model parameters, mean and standard error (SE) based on two-step regression (Bessason et al. 2020)

	β_0		β_1		θ_0		θ_1		θ'_0	
	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE
RC	-3.503	0.123	11.953	0.632	-1.774	0.031	0.305	0.023	1.645	0.024
Timber	-3.457	0.143	7.267	0.517	-2.315	0.025	0.103	0.025	1.894	0.027
Masonry	-3.025	0.259	11.370	1.357	-0.360	0.031	0.725	0.019	1.012	0.017

Figure 67 shows the uncertainty of the vulnerability curves. It should be noted that mean minus one standard deviation can result in negative DF values, especially at low PGA, which has no meaning (negative loss). This fact explains why beta-model is preferable to construct the statistical model.

Figure 66. Loss estimation curves for RC, timber, and masonry buildings in the Icelandic testbed.

Figure 67. Comparison of the mean curve (solid black line), prediction interval with 84,13% upper and 15,87% lower prediction bounds (green area) and mean + plus one standard deviation curve (dotted line).

From the statistical model and ($P[X > x] = 1 - P[X < x]$) it is also possible to construct fragility curves which can be used for comparison with other studies. To do this, it is however necessary to define damage states in form of loss bins. In Bessason et al. (2020) four damage states were defined using loss bins to define the damage states:

- DS0 - *minor*, loss of less than 1% of replacement value.
- DS1 - *slight*, loss in the range 1-5% of replacement value.
- DS2 - *moderate*, loss in the range 5-20% of replacement value.
- DS3 - *substantial*, loss in the range 20-50% of replacement value.

In Figure 68, these curves are shown for the three-building typologies.

Figure 68. Fragility curves based on the statistical model for RC, timber, and masonry buildings.

5.1.3 Results

5.1.3.1 Deterministic loss scenario for the 2008 Ölfus earthquake

On 29 May 2008, a Mw6.3 earthquake occurred on two almost parallel north-south oriented faults with a right-lateral strike-slip mechanism in Ölfus (South Iceland). The macroseismic epicentre was located between the towns of Selfoss and Hveragerði (Sigbjörnsson et al. 2009). The variation of PGA in the area was surprisingly high with a minimum between 0.45 to 0.53 g in the centre of Hveragerði to maximums of 0.76 to 0.84 g in the eastern and western parts of the city.

The earthquake did not cause any collapse of residential buildings or other structures, but extensive damage was observed (Sigbjörnsson et al. 2009), which exceeded that of the June 2000 earthquakes. Three villages were strongly affected (Hveragerði, Selfoss, and Eyrarbakki) and around 2000 buildings were damaged to some extent (25 of them were uninhabitable after the earthquake). The buildings with higher damage were those built of concrete or masonry with little or no reinforcement. Rupakhety et al. (2016) computed the simulated damage factor and obtained a mean damage factor of 6.8% for concrete, 4.0 % for timber and 14.2% for masonry and a combined damage factor of 6.4 (assuming that approximately 61, 32 and 7% of the total buildings were constructed using concrete, timber and masonry respectively).

Therefore, the SELENA software is used to run a simulation scenario for the 2008 Ölfus earthquake assuming a mean PGA in the city of Hveragerði of 0.66 g. The vulnerability functions used were proposed by Bessason et al. (2020). Appendix F describes the SELENA input files.

The obtained damage factors were 13% for concrete, 34% for masonry, and 6.9% for timber, and a mean damage factor of 12%. These results confirm that masonry buildings are the most vulnerable in the city. The large difference between the damage factor obtained by Rupakhety et al. (2016) for the combined three cities and the damage factor obtained only for Hveragerði may indicate a higher damage in this city than in Selfoss and Eyrarbakki so the average damage factor (6.4%) is lower.

Finally, although the vulnerability functions proposed by Bessason et al. (2020) tend to overestimate the damage (B. Bessason, *personal communication*), the obtained results are very similar to the real damage observed in the city so these vulnerability functions are used to compute the time-dependent loss curves during the 2000 seismic series.

5.1.3.2 Time-dependent risk scenario for Hveragerði during the 2000 seismic series.

The same logic tree proposed in the time-dependent seismic hazard for Hveragerði (Section 4.1.4.1) with corresponding weights has been used allowing to relate the exceedances of the computed PGA for each one of the daily probabilities of exceedance with the vulnerability functions provided by Bessason et al. (2020) and to compute the following risk metric: damage probabilities (none, slight, moderate, extensive and complete), damaged buildings (in each damage state), and the uninhabitable buildings (due to the type of fragility functions specifically obtained for the city, we have assumed that buildings with 100% of complete damage and 50% of extensive damage are uninhabitable). The mean damage ratio defined as the sum of the damage factor for each typology multiplied by the ratio between the built area of the typology to the total built area in the city is obtained in addition. Finally, the injuries to the population are obtained using a simplified model using injury rates and collapse rates taken from HAZUS (see Appendix F).

Figure 69 shows a summary of the results in terms of the mean damage ratio compared with the mean damage ratio from the conventional (time-independent) PSHA for the city. As we can see, the mean damage ratio curve for the conventional hazard has always lower daily probabilities of exceedances

than the curves for the TDPHSA during the days of the seismic series. The mean damage ratios are maximum for the first day after the mainshock (18 June) with a value of 8% for a daily probability of exceedance of 0.01, for example. It decreases from 19 to 21 June. Subsequently, it increase again, so the mean damage ratio during 22 June is similar to 20, and 23 June is similar to 21 June decreasing again on day 24 June with a daily probability of exceedance of 0.001 (again for the example of a mean damage ratio of 8%). This behaviour is related to the occurrence of the 21 June Mw6.5 earthquake which increased the daily probabilities of exceedances for the corresponding PGA and, therefore, increased the mean damage ratio.

Figure 69. Comparison of MDR curves for the different days of the seismic series and the conventional (time-independent seismic PSHA) curve

The mentioned behaviour can be better observed, if we choose for example a mean damage ratio of 10% and plot the time evolution for each day (Figure 70).

The detailed results for the different risk metrics can be found in Appendix G, Figure 74 to Figure 81. However, from the viewpoint of an OEF forecast, the MDR is not the best metric to take decisions on mitigation actions. Hence, the next subsection describes the chosen approach.

5.1.3.3 Cost-Benefit Analysis

As explained in Section 3.5.3.2, the probabilistic seismic risk curve (in terms of fatalities) is used to carry out a simplified cost-benefit analysis to determine if the mitigation action of the evacuation of the population for specific model building types is beneficial.

First, the daily probability of exceedance of a given number of fatalities was computed and compared with the cost-benefit analysis for the three possible costs of evacuation (\$20, \$50, and \$500). Figure 71 shows the obtained results for the first day after the mainshock (18 June) if the earthquake occurs at night (resulting in the highest number of fatalities). The yellow curves are the cost-benefit curves for each cost of evacuation. Subsequently, when the fatality curve is higher than the cost-benefit curve, the evacuation will be a beneficial action.

Figure 70 Time evolution of the daily probability of exceedance for a MDR= 10%

As we can see, even for the event occurring on 18 June, which has a higher seismic hazard, the evacuation is not beneficial from any building if we assume a cost of evacuation of \$500 p.p.d. However, it turns out that evacuation from the masonry, RC, and timber buildings is beneficial for most of the daily probabilities of exceedances if the cost is \$50 p.p.d or less. In any case, the timber buildings cause fewer fatalities never reaching one fatality for any of the daily probability of exceedance.

Alternatively, in order to make a decision during an ongoing crisis, and taking into consideration that the probability of fatalities changes continuously day by day, it will be easier to understand if we plot a time series of the probability of exceeding a given number of fatalities. To illustrate this, we chose the probability of exceeding 1 fatality in the corresponding typology. This corresponds to 0.8% of the population for masonry buildings, 0.06 % of the population living in RC, and 0.1% living in timber. These values are similar to those chosen by van Stiphout et al. (2010) who chose the probability of exceeding 100 fatalities from 72000 inhabitants in L'Aquila (i.e, 0.13 % of the total population).

As we can see in Figure 72, for masonry buildings the mitigation action of evacuation is always favourable if the cost \$20, it is only favourable for the first and second days if the cost is \$50 but it is never favourable for a cost of \$500 p.p.d .

On the other hand, the evacuation from RC buildings is never favourable in the most of the days and only it is favourable for the first day if the cost of evacuation is the minimum one (i.e \$20 p.p.d).

5.2 Software description

The software package is described in deliverable 3.5.

Figure 71. Cost-benefit analysis for the 18 June event using evacuation as the mitigation action for the three defined typologies.

Figure 72. Probability of Exceeding 1 fatality updated daily. Day 1 corresponds to 18/06/2000 and Day 0 corresponds to the results for a conventional PSHA-based loss curve.

5.3 Conclusions

As we have demonstrated from the viewpoint of the OEF, it is more useful to express the results in terms of a time-dependent loss curve, which can be easily transformed into a cost-benefit result that allows us to take a decision regarding any mitigation action. Finally, from the obtained results, we can conclude that the mitigation actions should be always focused on the weakest buildings.

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D3.4

Appendix

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Responsible Partner:	University of Alicante
Version:	2.0
Date:	11/12/2020
Distribution level:	Public

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Comments
13/11/2020	1.0	Sergio Molina	First Draft
11/12/2020	2.0	Sergio Molina	Second Draft
16/12/2020	3.0	Sergio Molina	Final Draft

LIST OF PARTNERS

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BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
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GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
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NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
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1 APPENDIX A. SENSITIVITY ANALYSES OF INFLUENTIAL VARIABLES IN SEISMICITY FORECASTING

1.1 Sensitivity to the adaptive prior estimation of ETAS parameters

To examine the influence of prior distribution on the resulting posterior instead of a fixed prior function, we account for the day-by-day adaptive learning procedure for estimation of daily prior parameters. For this reason, the starting mean values of the prior distribution which is used for forecasting the first forecasting interval (i.e. 18 June 2000) should be defined in advance. While for the subsequent forecasting intervals (from 19 to 25 June forecasting time windows), mean values of the posterior distribution of the day before are adaptively set to the mean prior values for the desired forecasting day, which means that the mean posterior of day n acts as a mean prior for seismicity forecasting of day $n+1$.

In this section, to assess the performance of the day-by-day adaptive learning priors, we employ two sets of ETAS model parameters as the initial values of the prior distribution parameters: 1) the best optimal estimates which are the optimal prior values as best estimates for the June 2000 seismic sequence, 2) the conventional ETAS model parameters (Eberhard 2014) calculated from plug-in estimation procedures for the whole Iceland. Table 1 and

Table 2 represent the mean and CV of the posterior distribution of the ETAS model parameters for eight forecasting intervals based on day-by-day adaptive learning priors using the initial mean priors of the optimal ETAS estimates (see Table 1) as well as the conventional ETAS parameters for Iceland (see Table 2), respectively. In Table 1 and

Table 2, for almost all parameters, CV decreases from 18 towards 25 June, and the final mean value of the parameters are in agreement with mean posterior distribution of the day before.

Table 1: Posterior statistics of ETAS parameters based on daily adaptive priors for eight forecasting intervals using the optimal ETAS parameter estimates as the initial mean priors

	β		c		p		d		q		K		K_t		K_r	
	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV
Initial Priors	1.2	0.3	0.005	0.3	1.2	0.3	0.8	0.3	1.6	0.3						
18 June 2000	0.982	0.034	0.005	0.276	1.242	0.076	0.987	0.11	1.576	0.04	0.702	0.406	0.063	0.097	0.184	0.21
19 June 2000	1.069	0.032	0.005	0.321	1.2	0.05	0.801	0.081	1.581	0.022	0.603	0.193	0.067	0.069	0.144	0.124
20 June 2000	1.093	0.03	0.005	0.201	1.204	0.035	0.77	0.08	1.567	0.023	0.551	0.117	0.068	0.04	0.135	0.128
21 June 2000	1.106	0.026	0.006	0.231	1.217	0.038	0.924	0.058	1.662	0.014	0.527	0.123	0.069	0.046	0.19	0.089
22 June 2000	1.093	0.026	0.004	0.265	1.17	0.037	0.739	0.089	1.564	0.027	0.594	0.137	0.065	0.066	0.129	0.145
23 June 2000	1.098	0.022	0.004	0.227	1.173	0.033	0.7	0.108	1.546	0.032	0.57	0.124	0.065	0.05	0.119	0.17

24 June 2000	1.101	0.021	0.004	0.233	1.168	0.03	0.759	0.132	1.587	0.039	0.57	0.124	0.064	0.063	0.138	0.217
25 June 2000	1.106	0.02	0.004	0.17	1.188	0.023	0.725	0.072	1.563	0.021	0.526	0.075	0.066	0.034	0.125	0.113

Table 2: Posterior statistics of ETAS parameters based on daily adaptive priors for 8 forecasting intervals using the conventional ETAS parameters proposed by Eberhard (2014) as the initial mean priors

	β		c		p		d		q		K		K_t		K_r	
	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV
Initial Priors	0.1723	0.3	0.0318	0.3	1.488	0.3	0.0064	0.3	2.5633	0.3						
18 June 2000	0.718	0.043	0.019	0.436	1.823	0.128	0.02	0.063	1.124	0.026	0.657	0.047	0.033	0.28	0.015	0.056
19 June 2000	1.062	0.028	0.008	0.267	1.266	0.042	0.073	0.063	1.177	0.009	0.529	0.082	0.071	0.043	0.022	0.025
20 June 2000	1.091	0.03	0.007	0.236	1.224	0.034	0.238	0.061	1.29	0.014	0.535	0.098	0.072	0.039	0.04	0.042
21 June 2000	1.099	0.027	0.005	0.209	1.197	0.029	0.511	0.071	1.446	0.021	0.55	0.092	0.069	0.04	0.078	0.083
22 June 2000	1.093	0.025	0.004	0.192	1.179	0.023	0.7	0.071	1.544	0.024	0.568	0.092	0.067	0.038	0.118	0.111
23 June 2000	1.101	0.021	0.003	0.276	1.138	0.036	0.76	0.09	1.582	0.027	0.651	0.176	0.06	0.114	0.136	0.149
24 June 2000	1.103	0.023	0.003	0.165	1.159	0.025	0.718	0.087	1.56	0.028	0.578	0.096	0.064	0.044	0.124	0.143
25 June 2000	1.105	0.021	0.004	0.247	1.179	0.024	0.742	0.071	1.578	0.023	0.54	0.087	0.066	0.048	0.131	0.112

1.2 Comparison amongst three scenarios of prior knowledge utilization

Figure 1 exhibits a statistical comparison between three scenarios of prior distribution as follows: a) fixed non-adaptive optimal priors, b) daily adaptive priors with initial values of optimal ETAS estimates, c) daily adaptive priors with starting values of the conventional ETAS parameters, for 24-hour forecasting intervals. Daily prior mean values and their corresponding standard deviations are plotted for all scenarios.

It is explicitly apparent that the conventional ETAS model parameters proposed for Iceland are not reliable for forecasting the early days of the June 2000 seismic sequence due to its significant difference with the best estimates of ETAS parameters. The trends of the daily adaptive priors illustrate how well the Bayesian-based seismicity forecasting framework is trying to capture the sequence daily.

Figure 1 elucidates that the adaptive prior system is superior to the non-adaptive prior system because even for a poor starting value (black line) the daily learning process leads to values very close to the optimal ETAS model estimates.

Figure 1. Comparison of three scenarios of prior information (see legend) incorporated in the Bayesian-based ETAS parameter estimation procedure for daily forecasting intervals during the June 2000 seismic sequences. Mean values (symbols) and standard deviations (shaded area) are plotted by similar colour for each scenario.

We also compared the resultant seismicity forecasts for the three scenarios of a, b and c. There are negligible differences between the spatial distribution of seismicity forecasts generated from fixed non-adaptive optimal ETAS priors and the daily adaptive priors with the same starting values of the optimal ETAS priors. However, for forecasting interval of 18 June 2000, the scenario c appears to result in very spotty spatial seismicity forecasts which differs remarkably with the seismicity forecast maps associated with scenarios a and b. This is a direct consequence of using poor initial priors. Also, the model does not have enough time or data to tune adaptively, immediately after a strong earthquake.

Therefore, to attain a reliable forecast at early aftershock period, it is imperative to have optimal priors based on a calibrated Bayesian ETAS model to be prepared for the next sequence. That is the basis for more reliable one-day seismicity forecasts.

For the 21 June forecasting interval, both daily-adaptive-based procedures (i.e. scenario b and c) tunes satisfactorily and result in an acceptable forecasts as the adaptive prior scheme have the required time and data to tune and hence, improves the seismicity forecasts.

1.3 Sensitivity to the area of the zone for calculation of the spatial forecasted probability of an earthquake

In this section, in Figure 2, we plotted the probability of having at least one earthquake with $M_w \geq 4.5$ per four zones with different area, i.e. 20 km², 50 km², 100 km² and 200 km², covering various numbers of grid cells. The forecasting time interval is 18 June 2000 in all maps.

Figure 2. Spatial forecasts of the probability of having at least one earthquake with $M_w \geq 4.5$ per 20, 50, 100 and 200 km² for 18 June 2000 forecasting time interval.

Based on the results, for the south Iceland aftershock zone, the 20 km² is the maximum zone based on the seismicity and fault pattern of south Iceland. Moreover, the 20 km² area results in an optimal spatial distribution of the forecasts considering the grid cell size of the predefined aftershock zone, because its spatial distribution is approximately similar to the forecasted seismicity distribution, only with a smoother pattern. Herein, we emphasize that the optimal area of the zone depends on the fault pattern, size of the area of the under-study region (i.e. aftershock zone area) and the grid cell size. For larger grid cell, the zone over which the calculation of the forecasted probability is performed, should set to a broader area.

1.4 Sensitivity to the number of posterior samples

The spatial seismicity maps corresponding to the forecasting interval of 21 June 2000 are generated based on MCMC sampling of ETAS parameters with 220, 1000 and 2000 number of updating iterations. To realistically evaluate the convergence and stability of the ETAS parameters' posteriors, the trace plots, Gelman Rubin and autocorrelation analyses are presented for the considered scenarios in Figure 3. Note that the number of Markov chains is 5 for all scenarios.

As seen in Figure 3, for a larger number of iterations (i.e. 1000 and 2000), the histogram of all ETAS parameters' posterior samples, are highly well-determined presenting superior unimodal and symmetric posterior densities compared to the 220 iterations scenario (default number of samples utilized in the daily forecasting analyses).

Furthermore, scrutiny of the convergence diagnostic results shows that the Gelman–Rubin statistic is below the range of 1.05 for the vast number of iterations and the degree of autocorrelation is very small (in most cases reaches less than 0.05). Such robust sampling provides reliable estimates of the ETAS parameters with low uncertainties and consequently results in the robust seismic forecast.

Based on the convergence diagnostic results, it is apparent that the ETAS model parameters converge better as the number of MCMC updating iterations increases. However, for the development of an operational earthquake forecasting, it is recommended to use the optimal number of posterior samples considering the long computation time for a large number of sampling such as 1000 iterations. To understand the influence of number of iterations in the resultant daily seismicity forecasts, the spatial distribution of the probability of at least one earthquake with a magnitude above 4 and 6 are compared in Figure 4 for two scenarios of 220 and 1000 posterior samples.

According to Figure 4, the resultant spatial forecasted earthquake probabilities do not differ significantly. Moreover, the daily forecasted probabilities over the entire region reported on the left bottom side of each panel are almost the same for both scenarios.

To conclude, we believe that running 5 chains of length 1000 is sufficient to obtain stable parameters. However, if one can select good starting values, then 5 chains of length 220 with burn-in of 10% of the total length of a chain can be usable in practice provided the Metropolis-Hastings steps are well-tuned. Note that all the above analyses repeated for the number of posterior samples smaller than 200, e.g. 50. However, the ETAS model parameters did not converge satisfactorily, and the forecast results were not acceptable. Therefore, for the sake of brevity, the results are not presented in this report.

Note that here the spatial forecasts are generated from the absolute value of seismicity neglecting the impact of the area of grid cell. Therefore, the final estimates of the probability of earthquakes need to be modified and validated.

Figure 3. Convergence diagnostic results for seismicity forecasting of 21 June 2000 for three scenarios of 1000 and 2000 number of posterior samples.

Figure 4. Forecasted probability of having at least one earthquake with $M_w \geq 4.0$ (first row) and $M_w \geq 6.0$ (2nd row) on 21 June 2000 for 220 and 1000 number of posterior samples.

1.5 Sensitivity to the number of Markov chains

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the ETAS model parameters using diagnostic analyses by increasing the number of Markov chains used in the MCMC sampling algorithm. The results are investigated for two scenarios of 5 and 20 number of Markov chains. The number of sampling iterations is around 200 for both scenarios. Based on the results, there is no apparent improvement in the convergence and stability of the ETAS parameters by increasing the chain number. Moreover, the c parameter convergence worsens for 20 number of chains. Thus, we believe that 5 number of chains are sufficient to attain the optimal forecasting performance.

Figure 5. Convergence diagnostic results for seismicity forecasting of 21 June 2000 for two scenarios of 5 and 20 number of chains in MCMC sampling algorithm.

1.6 Sensitivity to the aftershock zone

Throughout this report, the whole SISZ and RPOR are defined as the aftershock zone for the June 2000 seismic sequence due to large scatter of the aftershock in the south Iceland region. However, in this section, we confined the aftershock zone to the two active N-S oriented faults that triggered the 17 and 21 June events. The new confined aftershock is described by longitude: [-21.05, -20.2] and latitude: [63.74, 64.23] ranges. Note that the input catalogue is also restricted to the confined aftershock zone.

Figure 6 shows the posterior distribution of ETAS parameters along with their corresponding prior distribution (blue curves). The prior distribution is updated adaptively on a daily basis using the posterior and standard deviation of one day before to create the prior of the interested forecasting interval. Figure 6 illustrates an incredibly well distribution of the ETAS parameters' posteriors.

Figure 7 shows the daily seismicity forecasts for earthquake with $M_w \geq 5.5$ in SISZ. These figures can be compared with the forecasts of section 4.3-section (a) which are generated for the same scenario except for the larger aftershock zone area (SISZ+RPOR). For the first four forecasting intervals (18, 19, 20 and 21 June), i.e. before the 21 June event incorporated with the ETAS forecasting calculation, the aftershock zone of the whole south Iceland region seems to be a superior choice as the simulated number of events above magnitude 2.0 are closer to their corresponding mean value compared to ones from the confined aftershock zone of merely SISZ. This observation is in agreement with the geographical distribution of triggered aftershocks occurred on 17 June 2000 immediately after the strong shock (less than 2 minutes) that extended to the southwestern Iceland, the RPOR region. However, for forecasting intervals of 22nd June and after, the discrepancy between the forecasted seismicity calculated from both aftershock zones decreases and reach a similar level of agreement between the actual and estimated number of events. This is chiefly due to the more restricted geographical distribution of the aftershocks triggered immediately after 21 June mainshock.

Figure 6: Posterior of ETAS parameters based on daily adaptive prior procedure for the confined aftershock zone (i.e. SISZ)

Figure 7. Daily forecasted seismicity for earthquake with $M_w \geq 5.5$ in SISZ for eight 24-hour forecasting intervals.

1.7 Sensitivity to the lower cut-off magnitude (M_l)

The forecasting analyses are performed for three scenarios of lower cut-off magnitude of 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5. The forecasting time window is the entire 24-hour of 21 June 2000. Note that for all scenarios, M_l is considered equal to M_c . Results are derived for 220 samples and 5 Markov chains. In the following we discussed the influence of M_l on the resultant seismicity forecast. Figure 8 shows the posterior and prior PDF of ETAS parameters and Figure 9 shows the convergence diagnostic results for the considered three scenarios.

Figure 8. Posterior and prior PDF of ETAS parameters for M_l equal to 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5.

It is apparent that the posterior PDF changes for different values of M_l . In particular, for M_l 2.5 distribution of parameters c , p and d are not well-determined. Furthermore, in Figure 9, compared to for M_l 2.0 convergence results (see section 4.3.4), the Gelman Rubin statistic doesn't show good mixing, especially for the spatial term parameters (i.e. d and q) for M_l 1.5 and almost all parameters for M_l 2.5. This is mainly because of insufficient number of events with a magnitude larger than 2.5 required for the model updating purposes as apparent from Figure 9. Moreover, M_l 1.5 is smaller than the magnitude of completeness of the catalogue (i.e. M_c 2.0 Figure 9). which results in diverge forecasting.

To explore the influence of M_l in the resultant seismicity forecasts, the spatial distribution of the probability of one or more large earthquake for 21 June 2000 are compared for three scenarios of M_l 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5. As expected, the seismicity forecasts differ significantly. Besides the spatial forecasted probability, the forecasted probability over the entire aftershock zone differs remarkably for different M_l values. Also, it should be highlighted that for small magnitude threshold, the computational effort for updating the spatiotemporal ETAS parameters increases significantly. Therefore, we conclude that for selecting reliable M_l with sufficient accuracy, several factors should be taken into consideration, namely: the M_c calculation at the time of issuing each forecast, computation time, gaining enough data for ETAS parameter updating, and its effect on the forecasted seismicity values. For retrospective study on the June 2000 seismic sequence, M_l 2.0 is the proper choice which is equal to the M_c of the seismic catalogue at the time of issuing daily forecasts.

Figure 9. Convergence diagnostic results for seismicity forecasting of 21 June 2000 for two scenarios of $M_l 1.5$ (1st row) and $M_l 2.5$ (2nd row).

1.8 Sensitivity to the cell size of the aftershock zone

Throughout the report, the default grid cell size of $0.0227^\circ \times 0.01^\circ$ (Lat, Long) is utilized. For Iceland, such cell size represents a square cell with 1.25 km^2 area.

In this section, we explore the influence of grid cell size (area of a cell) on the resultant forecasts. In this regard, we compare the seismicity forecasts of earthquakes with $M_w \geq 5.5$ for 21 June 2000 24-hour forecasting interval calculated for three different cell sizes: 1) a square-shape cell with 25 km^2 area (dimensions of $\sim 0.045^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$), 2) a square-shape cell with 1.25 km^2 area (dimensions of $\sim 0.0227^\circ \times 0.01^\circ$) which is the default size of this report, 3) a square-shape cell with 0.55 km^2 (dimensions of $\sim 0.0151^\circ \times 0.00664^\circ$).

For both forecasting intervals, by decreasing the cell area, the estimated probability of experiencing a specific strong/week earthquake (see $Pr(M > m)$ in the bottom left corner of the panels) diminishes gradually for almost all cases. However, as expected, the cell area directly impacts the resolution of the spatial distribution of the forecasted seismicity.

The smaller the cell area, the higher the spatial resolution of forecasts maps and the longer the computation time of the forecasting procedure. Therefore, to detect the optimal cell area, the sensitivity of the forecast's results should be considered.

Comparing the estimated probability of having an earthquake larger a defined threshold across the whole aftershock, we realize that the discrepancy between the smaller cell areas is negligible compared to the larger cell area. Moreover, As can be seen in Figure 11, the posterior distribution of the larger cell area (25 km^2) is not symmetric and well-distributed, especially for c and d parameters. Hence, for south Iceland region, a square-shape cell with an area of 1.25 km^2 ($\sim 0.0227^\circ \times 0.01^\circ$) is selected as the optimal cell size because analyses based on smaller cell size (e.g. 0.55 km^2) does not illustrate significantly higher resolution of forecasts map and also the expected number of events above 2.0 is almost similar to the one obtained from the cell area of 1.25 km^2 .

It should be emphasized that the above forecasting results are normalized to the cell area. However, ignoring the impact of the cell area results in completely different results (e.g. expected number of event). The forecasted seismic sequence varies noticeably by cell area at which events are simulated. For instance, in such case, using a cell size of $1.25 \text{ km} \times 1.25 \text{ km}$ (larger than unity), the forecasted seismicity extremely underestimates the total and cell-based number of simulated earthquakes.

Figure 10. Spatial seismicity forecasts for 18 June forecasting interval for grid cell area of 25 km², 1.25 km² and 0.55 km².

Figure 11. Posterior and prior distribution of five main ETAS parameters for forecasting intervals of 18 June (top window) and 21 June 2000 (2nd window) calculated based on cell area of 0.55 km², 1.25 km², and 25 km².

2 APPENDIX B. Complementary results of Reasenberg and Jones 1989 model for TB4

Figure 12. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=5.2$ in 29th June 1981, sequence 'B', (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 13. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenberg and Jones model during the Mm=5.2 in 29th June 1981, sequence 'B', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 14. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=6.8$ in 17th January 1983, sequence ‘C’, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 15. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=6.8 in 17th January 1983, sequence 'C', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 16. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=6.2$ in 23rd March 1983, sequence 'D', (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 17. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=6.2 in 23rd March 1983, sequence 'D', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 18. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=5.2$ in 2nd January 1984, sequence 'E', (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 19. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenberg and Jones model during the Mm=5.2 in 2nd January 1984, sequence 'E', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 20. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=5.6$ in 11th February 1984, sequence ‘F’, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 21. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=5.6 in 11th February 1984, sequence 'F', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 22. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=5.8$ in 16th October 1988, sequence ‘G’, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 23. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=5.8 in 16th October 1988, sequence 'G', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 24. Aftershock forecasting during the Mw=5.6 in 23rd January 1992, sequence ‘H’, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 25. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=5.6 in 23rd January 1992, sequence 'H', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 26. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=5.4$ in 26th March 1993, sequence ‘I’, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 27. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=5.4 in 26th March 1993, sequence 'I', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 28. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=6.5$ in 15th June 1995, sequence 'J', (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 29. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=6.5 in 15th June 1995, sequence 'J', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 30. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=6.6$ in 18th November 1997, sequence 'K', (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 31. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenberg and Jones model during the Mm=6.6 in 18th November 1997, sequence 'K', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 32. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=5.5$ in 14th August 2003, sequence 'L', (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 33. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=5.5 in 14th August 2003, sequence 'L', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

Figure 34. Aftershock forecasting during the $M_m=5.0$ in 17th April 2006, sequence ‘M’, (top): the magnitude of the observed events during ten days after the mainshock, (middle): daily forecast (and comparison with the observed data) of earthquakes with magnitude greater than the magnitude of completeness, (bottom): Magnitude of completeness of the earthquake catalogue in the forecast interval.

Figure 35. Bayesian updating of the aftershock parameters in Reasenber and Jones model during the Mm=5.0 in 17th April 2006, sequence 'M', (top-left): magnitude-frequency distribution (b-value), (top-right): productivity (a-value), (bottom-left): temporal decay (p-value), (bottom -right): time-scale (c-value).

3 APPENDIX C. Complementary results of ETAS model for TB4

Figure 36. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 26th February 1981 (Sequence A). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 37. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 30th June 1981 (Sequence B). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 38. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 18th January 1983 (Sequence C). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 39. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 24th March 1983 (Sequence D). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 40. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 2nd February 1984 (Sequence E). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 41. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 3rd November 1984 (Sequence F). The forecasting interval is 24hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 42. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 17th October 1988 (Sequence G). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 43. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 24th January 1992 (Sequence H). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 44. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 27th March 1993 (Sequence I). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 45. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 16th June 1995 (Sequence J). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 46. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 19th November 1997 (Sequence K). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 47. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 15th August 2003 (Sequence L). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 48. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 18th April 2006 (Sequence M). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 49. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 9th June 2008 (Sequence N). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

Figure 50. The spatial distribution of seismicity in the aftershock zone for 27th January 2014 (Sequence O). The forecasting interval is 24 hours starting from 0.00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude greater than or equal to a given magnitude is also shown at the bottom of the figure starting from $M=3.6$ which is the magnitude of completeness, and 7.5 as the maximum magnitude.

4 APPENDIX D. Complementary results of short-term hazard model for TB4

Figure 51. Short-term PSHA for Sequence A, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 52. Short-term PSHA for Sequence B, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 53. Short-term PSHA for Sequence C, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 54. Short-term PSHA for Sequence D, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 55. Short-term PSHA for Sequence E, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 56. Short-term PSHA for Sequence F, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 57. Short-term PSHA for Sequence G, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 58. Short-term PSHA for Sequence H, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 59. Short-term PSHA for Sequence I, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 60. Short-term PSHA for Sequence J, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 61. Short-term PSHA for Sequence K, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 62. Short-term PSHA for Sequence L, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 63. Short-term PSHA for Sequence M, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 64. Short-term PSHA for Sequence N, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

Figure 65. Short-term PSHA for Sequence O, (top-left): conventional annual probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (top-right): conventional annual rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with ESHM13 data, (bottom-left): short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve, and (bottom-right): short-term time-dependent daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional hazard curve.

5 APPENDIX E. Complementary results of non-seismic model

Moving average filter (60-days window)

Moving average filter (80-days window)

Figure 66. Logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with $M \geq 4.5$ using different window lengths for the moving average filter. Training time series.

Moving average filter (15-days window)

Moving average filter (30-days window)

Moving average filter (45-days window)

Moving average filter (60-days window)

Moving average filter (80-days window)

Figure 67. Logarithm of the daily seismic activity rate with $M \geq 5.0$ using different window lengths for the moving average filter. Training time series.

6 APPENDIX F. SELENA input files for the city of Hveragerði

Number of builindgs in Hveragerði (numbuild.txt)

%GEOUNIT	MSRY	RC	W	NONE
1	45	595	345	86

Built area (m²) in Hveragerði (builtarea.txt)

%GEOUNIT	MSRY	RC	W	NONE
1	8100.7	96369.7	51404.31	875.9

Population in Hveragerði (population.txt)

%GEOUNIT	POPULATION	DAYTIME_RES	NIGHTTIME_RES
1	2699	135	2564

Computation parameters (cpfile.txt)

% RISK ESTIMATION (1 Sd-based; 2 Sa-based; 3 PGA-based 4 Iceland-testbed) PERF. POINT COMP METHOD (1 N2M; 2 MADRS; 3 I-DCM), TYPE OF DAMAGE RESULT (1-SQM; 2-N of Blds.) HUMAN LOSSES MODEL (1-BASIC; 2-HAZUS) TOPOGRAPHY (1-EUROCODE; 2- ITALIAN CODE) SPECTRUM (1-UHS/Specific; 2-Conditional Mean Spectrum)

4 1 1 1 1 1

Population distribution by building typology and residential occupancy (occmbtp1.txt)

%GEOUNIT	MSRY	RC	W	NONE
1	0.046035806	0.618073316	0.330775789	0.00511509

Population distribuion for any type of occupancy (ocupmbtp.txt)

%No	RESIDENTIAL	COMERCIAL	EDUCATIONAL	Label
1	0.046035806	0	0	%MSRY
2	0.618073316	0	0	%RC
3	0.330775789	0	0	%W

Population distribution by hour of the day (poptime.txt)

%HOUR	INDOOR	OUTDOOR	Label
1	0.95	0.05	% night 02:00 am
2	0.10	0.80	% day 10:00 am
3	0.70	0.30	% commuting 17:00 pm

Type of soil in Hveragerði (solcenter1.txt)

%GEOUNIT	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE	SOIL	Vs30(m/s)	vsflag(0/1)	Z1_0(m)
geom(0/1/2/3)	place(0/1/2)	H(m)	L(m)	tc(1/2)	Tcorner(s)	
1	64.00	-21.191	1	800	0	800
	0	0	100	1	0	0

%Ground motion values at Hveragerði (tdlha.txt)

%IMlab	Geounit	Lat	Lon	PGA	Sa0.1	Sa0.15	Sa0.2	Sa0.25	Sa0.3	Sa0.4	Sa0.5	Sa0.75	Sa1.0
	Sa2.0	Sa3.0	Sa4.0										
1	1	64	-21.191	0.005	0	0	0	0	0.0125	0	0	0	0.005
	0	0	0										
2	1	64	-21.191	0.01	0	0	0	0	0.025	0	0	0	0.01
	0	0	0										
3	1	64	-21.191	0.03	0	0	0	0	0.075	0	0	0	0.03
	0	0	0										
4	1	64	-21.191	0.05	0	0	0	0	0.125	0	0	0	0.05
	0	0	0										
5	1	64	-21.191	0.07	0	0	0	0	0.175	0	0	0	0.07
	0	0	0										
6	1	64	-21.191	0.1	0	0	0	0	0.25	0	0	0	0.1
	0	0	0										
7	1	64	-21.191	0.12	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0.12
	0	0	0										
8	1	64	-21.191	0.14	0	0	0	0	0.35	0	0	0	0.14
	0	0	0										
9	1	64	-21.191	0.16	0	0	0	0	0.4	0	0	0	0.16
	0	0	0										
10	1	64	-21.191	0.18	0	0	0	0	0.45	0	0	0	0.18
	0	0	0										
11	1	64	-21.191	0.2	0	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0.2
	0	0	0										
12	1	64	-21.191	0.22	0	0	0	0	0.55	0	0	0	0.22
	0	0	0										
13	1	64	-21.191	0.24	0	0	0	0	0.6	0	0	0	0.24
	0	0	0										
14	1	64	-21.191	0.26	0	0	0	0	0.65	0	0	0	0.26
	0	0	0										
15	1	64	-21.191	0.28	0	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0	0.28
	0	0	0										

16	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0.75	0	0	0	0.3
17	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.32	0	0	0	0	0.8	0	0	0	0.32
18	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.34	0	0	0	0	0.85	0	0	0	0.34
19	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.36	0	0	0	0	0.9	0	0	0	0.36
20	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.38	0	0	0	0	0.95	0	0	0	0.38
21	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.4
22	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.42	0	0	0	0	1.05	0	0	0	0.42
23	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.44	0	0	0	0	1.1	0	0	0	0.44
24	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.46	0	0	0	0	1.15	0	0	0	0.46
25	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.48	0	0	0	0	1.2	0	0	0	0.48
26	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.5	0	0	0	0	1.25	0	0	0	0.5
27	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.52	0	0	0	0	1.3	0	0	0	0.52
28	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.54	0	0	0	0	1.35	0	0	0	0.54
29	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.56	0	0	0	0	1.4	0	0	0	0.56
30	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.58	0	0	0	0	1.45	0	0	0	0.58
31	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.6	0	0	0	0	1.5	0	0	0	0.6
32	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.62	0	0	0	0	1.55	0	0	0	0.62
33	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.64	0	0	0	0	1.6	0	0	0	0.64
34	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.66	0	0	0	0	1.65	0	0	0	0.66

35	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.68	0	0	0	0	1.7	0	0	0	0.68
36	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.7	0	0	0	0	1.75	0	0	0	0.7
37	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.72	0	0	0	0	1.8	0	0	0	0.72
38	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.74	0	0	0	0	1.85	0	0	0	0.74
39	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.76	0	0	0	0	1.9	0	0	0	0.76
40	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.78	0	0	0	0	1.95	0	0	0	0.78
41	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.8	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.8
42	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.82	0	0	0	0	2.05	0	0	0	0.82
43	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.84	0	0	0	0	2.1	0	0	0	0.84
44	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.86	0	0	0	0	2.15	0	0	0	0.86
45	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.88	0	0	0	0	2.2	0	0	0	0.88
46	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.9	0	0	0	0	2.25	0	0	0	0.9
47	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.92	0	0	0	0	2.3	0	0	0	0.92
48	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.94	0	0	0	0	2.35	0	0	0	0.94
49	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.96	0	0	0	0	2.4	0	0	0	0.96
50	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	0.98	0	0	0	0	2.45	0	0	0	0.98
51	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1	0	0	0	0	2.5	0	0	0	1
52	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.02	0	0	0	0	2.55	0	0	0	1.02
53	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.04	0	0	0	0	2.6	0	0	0	1.04

54	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.06	0	0	0	0	2.65	0	0	0	1.06
55	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.08	0	0	0	0	2.7	0	0	0	1.08
56	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.1	0	0	0	0	2.75	0	0	0	1.1
57	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.12	0	0	0	0	2.8	0	0	0	1.12
58	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.14	0	0	0	0	2.85	0	0	0	1.14
59	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.16	0	0	0	0	2.9	0	0	0	1.16
60	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.18	0	0	0	0	2.95	0	0	0	1.18
61	1 0	64 0	-21.191 0	1.2	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1.2

Severity 1 injury rate for each damage degree (injury1.txt)

%No	Slight	Moderate	Extensive	Complete	Complete-Collapse	Label
1	0.05	0.35	2	10	40	%MSRY
2	0.05	0.25	1	5	40	%RC
3	0.05	0.25	1	5	40	%W

Severity 2 injury rate for each damage degree (injury2.txt)

%No	Slight	Moderate	Extensive	Complete	Complete-Collapse	Label
1	0	0.4	0.2	2	20	%MSRY
2	0	0.03	0.1	1	20	%RC
3	0	0.03	0.1	1	20	%W

Severity 3 injury rate for each damage degree (injury3.txt)

%No	Slight	Moderate	Extensive	Complete	Complete-Collapse	Label
1	0	0.001	0.002	0.02	5	%MSRY
2	0	0	0.001	0.01	5	%RC
3	0	0	0.001	0.01	5	%W

Severity 4 injury rate for each damage degree (injury4.txt)

%No	Slight	Moderate	Extensive	Complete	Complete-Collapse	Label
1	0	0.001	0.002	0.02	10	%MSRY
2	0	0	0.001	0.01	10	%RC
3	0	0	0.001	0.01	5	%W

Collapse rate for complete damage (collapserate.txt)

%No.	COLLAPSE_RATE	LABEL(%)
1	15	%MSRY
2	14	%RC
3	3	%W

Price of new construction in Euros (newconstruction.txt)

%No	MSRY	RC	W	LABEL
1	900	2000	900	%RES

Price of repair/replacement complete damage by m² in Euros (elosscd.txt)

%No	MSRY	RC	W	LABEL
1	900	2000	900	%RES

Price of repair/replacement extensive damage by m² in Euros (elossed.txt)

%No	MSRY	RC	W	LABEL
1	675	1500	675	%RES

Price of repair/replacement moderate damage by m² in Euros (elossmd.txt)

%No	MSRY	RC	W	LABEL
1	225	500	225	%RES

Price of repair/replacement slight damage by m² in Euros (elosssd.txt)

%No	MSRY	RC	W	LABEL
1	45	100	45	%RES

7 APPENDIX G. Complementary results of time-dependent loss model

Figure 68. PSHA-based risk curve expressed in terms of uninhabitable buildings and mean damage ratio, number of buildings with complete damage, affected population and fatalities for the conventional PSHA.

Figure 69. PSHA-based risk curve expressed in terms of uninhabitable buildings and mean damage ratio, number of buildings with complete damage, affected population and fatalities for the the short term PSHA obtained 18 June 2000.

Figure 70. PSHA-based risk curve expressed in terms of uninhabitable buildings and mean damage ratio, number of buildings with complete damage, affected population and fatalities for the the short term PSHA obtained 19 June 2000.

Figure 71. PSHA-based risk curve expressed in terms of uninhabitable buildings and mean damage ratio, number of buildings with complete damage, affected population and fatalities for the the short term PSHA obtained 20 June 2000.

Figure 72. PSHA-based risk curve expressed in terms of uninhabitable buildings and mean damage ratio, number of buildings with complete damage, affected population and fatalities for the the short term PSHA obtained 20 June 2000.

Figure 73. PSHA-based risk curve expressed in terms of uninhabitable buildings and mean damage ratio, number of buildings with complete damage, affected population and fatalities for the the short term PSHA obtained 21 June 2000.

Figure 74. PSHA-based risk curve expressed in terms of uninhabitable buildings and mean damage ratio, number of buildings with complete damage, affected population and fatalities for the the short term PSHA obtained 22 June 2000.

Figure 75. PSHA-based risk curve expressed in terms of uninhabitable buildings and mean damage ratio, number of buildings with complete damage, affected population and fatalities for the the short term PSHA obtained 23 June 2000.

8 REFERENCES

Eberhard DAJ (2014) Multiscale Seismicity Analysis and Forecasting Examples from the Western Pacific and Iceland. 156. <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-a-010782581>